

FLEXBIT PROJECT

CETPartnership Joint Call 2023

Deliverable 1.2 – Current Regulatory Framework for Interoperability

Christina Karatrantou orcid: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9818-048X>

Pavlos Tyrologou orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7706-1774>

Nikolaos Koukouzas orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7094-3712>

Pio Alessandro Lombardi orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4598-9759>

Gaetano Zizzo orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4413-4855>

Pierluigi Gallo orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6333-5997>

Dimitrios Papadaskalopoulos orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7064-3429>

Tomasz Sikorski orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4423-7216>

Przemysław Janik orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5300-7845>

Marek Kott orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9865-4675>

Alexander Micallef orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9497-5604>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18323673

Status: Date 20/01/2025

Version: 1

This research was funded by CETPartnership, the Clean Energy Transition Partnership under the 2023 joint call for research proposals, co-funded by the European Commission (GA N°101069750) and with the funding organizations detailed on <https://cetpartnership.eu/funding-agencies-and-call-modules>.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Supported by:

Federal Ministry
for Economic Affairs
and Climate Action

Ministero delle Imprese
e del Made in Italy

on the basis of a decision
by the German Bundestag

FlexBIT Consortium

Università
degli Studi
di Palermo

TOR VERGATA
UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA

Wrocław University
of Science and Technology

L-Università
ta' Malta

CERTH
CENTRE FOR
RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY
HELLAS

UNIVERSITY OF
PATRAS
ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ ΠΑΤΡΩΝ

SCERG
Sustainable and Clean
Energy Research Group

Fraunhofer
IFF

Next
Multiservice

Arte
BESTATTUNGEN

electrum

Table of contents

FlexBIT Consortium.....	2
1 INTRODUCTION.....	5
1.1 Background.....	5
1.2 International status.....	6
1.3 Current energy infrastructure.....	7
1.4 Objectives and scope.....	8
2 THE EU ENERGY COMMUNITIES STRATEGY.....	10
2.1 Policy Strategy.....	10
2.2 Legislative context.....	11
2.3 Key trends and Implementation changes.....	16
2.4 Financial instruments and support mechanisms.....	17
3 REVIEW OF SEPERATE JURISDICTIONS.....	21
3.1 Italy.....	21
3.1.1 Overview.....	21
3.1.2 Key trends.....	21
3.1.3 Legal framework-barriers and opportunities.....	22
3.1.4 Alignment with cybersecurity and data protection rules.....	23
3.1.5 Permit process.....	23
3.1.6 Status of the market.....	24
3.1.7 Financial incentives.....	24
3.1.8 Cost of implementation.....	25
3.1.9 Estimated profit margin.....	26
3.2 Germany.....	27
3.2.1 Overview.....	27
3.2.2 Key trends.....	27
3.2.3 Legal framework-barriers and opportunities.....	28
3.2.4 Alignment with cybersecurity and data protection rules.....	29
3.2.5 Permit process.....	29
3.2.6 Status of the market.....	29
3.2.7 Financial incentives.....	30
3.2.8 Cost of implementation.....	30
3.2.9 Estimated profit margin.....	31
3.3 Malta.....	31
3.3.1 Overview.....	31
3.3.2 Key trends.....	31
3.3.3 Legal framework-barriers and opportunities.....	31
3.3.4 Alignment with cybersecurity and data protection rules.....	32
3.3.5 Permit process.....	32
3.3.6 Status of the market.....	32

3.3.7	Financial incentives	32
3.3.8	Cost of implementation	32
3.3.9	Estimated profit margin	33
3.4	Poland.....	33
3.4.1	Overview.....	33
3.4.2	Key trends.....	33
3.4.3	Legal framework-barriers and opportunities	34
3.4.4	Alignment with cybersecurity and data protection rules.....	36
3.4.5	Permit process.....	37
3.4.6	Status of the market.....	38
3.4.7	Financial incentives	39
3.4.8	Cost of implementation	40
3.4.9	Estimated profit margin.....	41
3.5	Greece	42
3.5.1	Overview.....	42
3.5.2	Key trends.....	42
3.5.3	Legal framework-barriers and opportunities	43
3.5.4	Alignment with cybersecurity and data protection rules.....	43
3.5.5	Permit process.....	44
3.5.6	Status of the market.....	44
3.5.7	Financial incentives	45
3.5.8	Cost of implementation	46
3.5.9	Estimated profit margin.....	47
4	COMPERATIVE ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS.....	49
4.1	Interoperability and data exchange challenges	49
4.2	Alingment with FlexBIT goals.....	49
5	CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS	51
5.1	Key findings.....	51
5.2	Policy and regulatory recommendations	51
5.3	Implementation roadmap for FlexBIT	52
6	REFERENCES.....	54
7	APPENDICES	59
7.1	Table of national legislation.....	59

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The European energy system is undergoing a profound transformation mainly due to renewables and electrification acceleration, the deployment of digital tools in grid operation and consumer services, and the increasing provision of flexibility by distributed assets (prosumers, SMEs, communities) rather than by centralised power plants. Together, these shifts reshape both system operation and the role of end-users in the market. Digitalisation encompasses the integration of advanced data, communication, and automation technologies, such as smart meters, Internet of Things (IoT) devices, cloud-edge computing, and AI-enabled optimisation, into all layers of the energy system, enabling real-time monitoring, forecasting, and coordinated system operation. Decentralisation promotes the shift from centralised, utility-driven generation to a distributed model where households, SMEs, energy communities, and local renewable plants actively participate as producers, consumers, or flexibility providers, thereby reshaping market dynamics and consumer roles across the Union. These trends are reshaping how energy is produced, distributed, and consumed by enabling decentralised renewable generation, real-time system optimisation, and consumer-centric market participation. As a result, new opportunities are emerging for citizens, local authorities, Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs), and communities, such as producing and sharing renewable electricity, providing demand-response and flexibility services, reducing energy costs through collective self-consumption, and participating in local energy markets supported by digital platforms and smart-grid technologies. Central to this evolution is the rise of individuals or organisations that both produce and consume energy, and the expansion of local renewable generation, storage, and flexibility services (Article 2, 21, 22 of Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001 (RED II)^[1] and Articles 2, 15, 16 of Electricity Directive (EU) 2019/944^[2]).

According to this, Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) have emerged as key instruments for achieving the objectives of the EU Green Deal^[3], specifically the acceleration of renewable energy deployment, the decarbonisation of the energy system, the empowerment of consumers, and the creation of a more flexible and decentralised electricity market, the Fit for 55 Package^[4], and the REPowerEU Plan^[5]. By enabling citizens to jointly produce, share, and manage renewable energy, energy communities strengthen energy democracy, increase public acceptance of renewable energy projects, decrease the cost for integrating electric power generated by volatile renewable energy sources, and contribute to social inclusiveness and energy poverty reduction.

However, the rapid growth of community energy also exposes several structural challenges related to regulatory harmonisation, data governance, cybersecurity, and digital interoperability. National transpositions of EU directives remain uneven, and the absence of standardised data-exchange procedures limits the ability of communities to engage in flexibility markets, energy-sharing schemes, and advanced digital services^[6].

FlexBIT project addresses these gaps by bridging the technical, regulatory, and digital dimensions of community energy. The project aims to establish an interoperable and cyber-secure framework that aligns with the Data Act (EU 2023/2854)^[7], NIS2 Directive (EU 2022/2555)^[8], GDPR^[9], and the provisions of RED II/III^[1, 10] and Directive 2019/944^[2], thereby supporting a coherent, citizen-centric energy transition across Europe.

1.2 International status

Globally, the transition toward decentralised, flexible, and digitally enabled energy systems is rapidly growing. International organisations, such as the International Energy Agency (IEA)^[11] and the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA)^[12] recognise community energy as a critical instrument for achieving net-zero emissions by 2050. Countries outside the EU, including the United States, Australia, and Japan, are deploying community solar schemes, virtual power plants, and local energy management systems, indicating a worldwide shift toward distributed energy resources (DERs) and consumer empowerment (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1: Global shift towards distributed energy resources (DERs) and consumer empowerment (qualitative overview).

The European Union leads at an international level the establishment of structured frameworks for community energy, with more than 7,000 operational energy communities across Member States^[6]. Early pioneers such as Denmark, Germany, and Italy demonstrate long-term maturity in cooperative and municipal renewable-energy models, driving innovation and shaping the policy landscape for other countries.

Digitalisation trends also play an influential role globally. The widespread deployment of advanced metering infrastructures, local energy markets, and interoperable data platforms is becoming essential for community energy growth. At the same time, cybersecurity risks and fragmented data frameworks highlight the need for robust governance mechanisms.

FlexBIT aligns with these global developments, contributing to Europe's international leadership in citizen-centred clean-energy innovation by supporting cross-border interoperability, regulatory convergence, digital energy services, and cyber-secure data exchange frameworks.

1.3 Current energy infrastructure

The current European energy infrastructure reflects a transitional system, which is characterised by declining fossil-fuel dependence and steadily rising renewable integration. In 2023, renewables reached 24.6% of gross final energy consumption, continuing an upward trend. They accounted for 46% of total EU energy production, making them the largest domestic energy source^[11]. Although this is a significant energy progress, the EU still relies on imported energy to cover up to 58% of its total energy needs, while the overall energy mix is composed of petroleum products (37.7%) and natural gas (20.4%)^[11]. These structural connections contribute significantly to regional gaps in terms of energy security, grid flexibility, and decarbonisation readiness across Member States (Figure 1.2).

Figure 1.2: EU energy mix and import dependency (EU-27, 2023)

Grid congestion, ageing distribution networks, and limited hosting capacity are the most common long-term challenges that persist. In addition, the wide variation in national energy mixes, ranging from Sweden’s 66.4% share of renewables in consumption to less than 15% in several western and southern Member States, emphasise to the uneven infrastructural and policy landscape that energy communities must explore. Together, these factors underline the need for interoperable, digitally enabled solutions that support secure data exchange, coordinated flexibility services, and efficient integration of decentralised energy assets across Europe^[11].

Digital readiness across the EU is similarly uneven. Some countries, such as Italy and Germany, have advanced data-management frameworks (e.g., TIAD^[13, 14], the Smart Meter Gateway System under MsbG^[15]), while others, including Poland and Malta, are still developing foundational digital infrastructures like national energy data hubs. Smart-meter rollout, a key enabler of real-time energy management, remains inconsistent across Member States (Figure 1.3).

Figure 1.3: Indicative digital readiness across FlexBIT member states (qualitative assessment based on this deliverable).

These gaps directly affect the operation of energy communities. In many regions, the lack of interoperability between Distributed System Operators (DSOs), aggregators, prosumers, and digital platforms hinders access to flexibility markets, energy-sharing schemes, and collective self-consumption models. Cybersecurity requirements under NIS2^[8] and data-exchange obligations under the Data Act^[7] add additional layers of complexity that require harmonised, secure implementation across jurisdictions.

FlexBIT addresses these gaps by defining concrete technical and organisational requirements for interoperable interfaces between community platforms, Distribution System Operators (DSOs), and aggregators. It establishes structured data-governance mechanisms for lawful data access and sharing in accordance with the GDPR and the Data Act. Additionally, specifies baseline cybersecurity controls aligned with the NIS2 Directive. Together, these elements enable consistent implementation across Member States and support the scalable deployment of digital community energy services.

1.4 Objectives and scope

FlexBIT aims to develop a harmonised, cyber-secure framework that supports data exchange, regulatory compliance, and cross-platform interoperability in line with the EU’s broader energy and digital policy objectives. FlexBIT intends to:

- Enable secure, standardised, and real-time data exchange across community energy platforms, DSOs, aggregators, and flexibility markets.

- Support compliance with the Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001 and (EU) 2023/2413, the Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944, the Data Act (EU) 2023/2854, NIS2 (EU) 2022/2555, and GDPR.
- Identify regulatory gaps, technical barriers, and cybersecurity requirements affecting community-based flexibility services and collective self-consumption.
- Provide a comparative, evidence-based analysis of Italy, Germany, Malta, Poland, and Greece, assessing legal frameworks, market maturity, financial incentives, digitalisation readiness, and permitting conditions.
- Deliver policy and regulatory recommendations to improve consistency across Member States and facilitate cross-border replication of community energy models.
- Demonstrate digital solutions and interoperable architectures that enhance grid resilience, promote citizen engagement, and support the development of sustainable local energy markets (Figure 1.4).

This deliverable aims to define the regulatory, technical, and institutional context for interoperable and digitally enabled energy communities in Europe.

Figure 1.4: Reference interoperable architecture for digitally enabled energy communities (actors, interfaces, and compliance overlay).

The objective of this deliverable is to provide a structural foundation for the integration of digitally enabled, community-driven energy systems into the European energy landscape. Through FlexBIT project, the promotion of a secure, inclusive, data-driven, and interoperable energy transition, supports directly to the EU's 2030 and 2050 climate goals.

2 The EU Energy Communities Strategy

2.1 Policy Strategy

The European Union's energy policy framework is rapidly developing to support a digital, decentralised, and decarbonised energy system aligned with the EU's 2030 and 2050 climate objectives. The strategic policy framework, described through the European Green Deal^[3], aims to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 while ensuring that citizens, local authorities, and communities actively participate in the energy transition. This citizen-centred approach is further supported by the Fit for 55 Package^[4], the REPowerEU Plan^[5], and complementary strategies that highlight system flexibility, secure data exchange, and energy democracy.

A major component of this policy direction is the transition from a centralised, supply-driven energy model to a distributed, interoperable architecture that integrates renewable energy production at the local level. The EU Strategy for Energy System Integration (2020)^[16] outlines in detail a framework where electricity, heating, cooling, transport, and industrial systems operate in coordination, supported by digital infrastructures that enable real-time data exchange, smart metering, and flexibility services. This integrated approach recognises that distributed energy resources, including those operated by energy communities, are essential for reducing system costs, enhancing resilience, and accelerating decarbonisation.

The Digitalisation of the Energy System Action Plan (2022)^[17] mentions the need for interoperable energy data spaces, cybersecurity measures, and common European data standards, which are crucial for enabling energy communities, aggregators, and prosumers to participate in electricity markets, offer flexibility services, and interact securely with Distribution System Operators (DSOs) and Transmission System Operators (TSOs). The Action Plan^[17] establishes a pathway towards the Common European Energy Data Space^[18], which will promote innovation, cross-border interoperability, and consumer empowerment through transparent and secure data sharing.

Energy communities are the core element of this transition. Through the Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001^[1] and 2023/2413^[10] and the Electricity Directive (EU) 2019/944^[2], the EU officially recognises Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) as new market actors with the legal right to produce, consume, share, and sell renewable energy across local and regional networks. The above directives establish the legal framework for collective self-consumption, peer-to-peer trading, and participation in flexibility markets, while ensuring that communities have non-discriminatory access to distribution networks.

In addition, the REPowerEU Plan (2022)^[5] strengthens the importance of local renewable generation by promoting faster permitting procedures, rapid deployment of rooftop PV, and expanded community-based energy models as tools to improve energy security and reduce dependency on imported fossil fuels. Energy communities are considered not only as social mechanisms for citizen participation, but also as advantageous frameworks that can provide decentralised demand-response potential, local balancing capacity, and enhanced system resilience.

Throughout these strategic EU legal frameworks, the EU outlines that digital infrastructure, data interoperability, and cybersecurity are mandatory for achieving a decentralised and flexible energy system. The synthesis of the Data Act (EU 2023/2854)^[7], NIS2 Directive (EU 2022/2555)^[8], Data Governance Act^[19], and forthcoming Energy Data Space^[18] ensures that energy communities can securely access, exchange, and process the data needed to participate meaningfully in modern electricity markets.

In summary, the EU's policy strategy determines a coherent concept in which local actors, prosumers, and energy communities are central drivers of decarbonisation, supported by a legal framework that facilitates digitalisation, interoperability, and secure data flows. This dynamically changing landscape sets out the foundation for projects such as FlexBIT, which implements these policy goals by developing practical architectures, tools, and governance models for citizen-centred, digitally enabled energy communities.

2.2 Legislative context

The EU's transition towards a decentralised, digital and decarbonized energy system is based on a set of interlinked legal instruments that define the rights, obligations, and responsibilities of energy communities and other market actors. This framework has been further strengthened by the adoption of the revised Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2023/2413^[10] (RED III), which entered into force in November 2023. RED III increases the EU's binding renewable energy target to at least 42.5% by 2030 and reinforces enabling provisions for renewable energy communities, including accelerated permitting procedures and stronger obligations for Member States to remove administrative barriers.

For FlexBIT, the most relevant components are:

- the energy regulatory framework (Directives (EU) 2018/2001^[1], 2019/944^[2] and Regulation (EU) 2019/943^[20]),
- the horizontal data and digital framework (GDPR^[9], Data Governance Act^[19], Data Act^[7], Digital Markets Act^[21]), and
- the cybersecurity regime (NIS2 Directive^[8] and the Network Code on Cybersecurity^[22]).

The above instruments define how energy communities may participate in the market, how data must be handled and shared, and how responsibilities are distributed across the system (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Allocation of rights, obligations and system responsibilities across key actors involved in energy communities under the EU legal framework.

The Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001^[1] (RED II), as amended by RED III^[10], introduces renewable self-consumers and renewable energy communities (RECs) and sets out the enabling conditions under which they operate. In parallel, the revised Energy Efficiency Directive (EU) 2023/1791^[23] introduces binding energy consumption reduction targets and strengthens the concept of “energy efficiency first”. These provisions are particularly relevant for energy communities, as they emphasise collective self-consumption, demand-side flexibility, and targeted support for vulnerable consumers and worst-performing buildings. Article 2 defines “renewable self-consumer” and “renewable energy community”, clarifying that RECs are autonomous legal entities controlled by members located in proximity to the renewable-based plants. In Article 22, it is mentioned that each Member State is required to put in place enabling frameworks for RECs, including non-discriminatory and proportionate network charges, access to all suitable electricity markets, fair, transparent and cost-reflective procedures, tools to facilitate access to finance and information, and removal of unjustified regulatory and administrative barriers. These provisions are directly relevant for FlexBIT, as they deploy the legal basis for community-driven flexibility services, energy sharing, and data-driven coordination.

The Electricity Directive 2019/944^[2] complements RED II/III by introducing citizen energy communities (CECs) and detailing the consumer-centred internal market design. According to Article 2, “citizen energy community” and related entities can engage in generation, distribution, supply, aggregation, storage and energy efficiency services, including EV charging, while being effectively controlled by citizens, local authorities or small enterprises. In Article 15, consumer rights are strengthened by participating in demand response and using aggregators, ensuring that consumers and communities can offer flexibility services without facing undue barriers. Article 16 mentions the obligation of each Member States to create enabling frameworks for CECs, guaranteeing voluntary and open participation, effective control by local members, non-discriminatory treatment vis-à-vis other market participants, the right to own, establish or lease distribution networks in specific circumstances, and the ability to share energy within the community while safeguarding consumer protection. Articles 31–32 refer to the distribution system operation, enforcing Distribution System Operators (DSOs) to ensure transparent and non-discriminatory connection and access conditions, and to use flexibility services as an alternative to traditional grid reinforcement were cost-effective. The above articles of the Electricity Directive^[2] define the way that energy communities are connected to the grid, participate in markets and interact with DSOs, and thus outline the technical and contractual environment that FlexBIT must consider when designing interoperable and cyber-secure solutions.

The Electricity Regulation (EU) 2019/943^[20] sets the holistic market design and system operation rules that also defines the environment for energy communities. In Article 3, the principles of an integrated, competitive, consumer-centred electricity market, emphasising non-discrimination and market-based dispatch are described in detail. Articles 6–8 mention the rules for balancing, capacity allocation and congestion management, and thus establishing the framework within which flexibility and balancing services (potentially provided by communities and aggregators) must operate. In accordance with Articles 12–13, responsibilities of transmission and distribution system operators in maintaining system security, non-discriminatory access and transparent rules for congestion management and capacity calculation are clarified. From a system-liability perspective, these regulatory elements determine which actors are responsible for system security, congestion management and balancing, and how new actors such as energy communities must align with these responsibilities when offering flexibility or engaging in local energy markets.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)^[9] controls any processing of personal data, including metering data and consumption profiles linked to identifiable individuals involved in energy communities. Articles 5 and 6 of GDPR, set out the legal fundamentals for processing (lawfulness, fairness, transparency, purpose limitation, data minimisation, storage limitation and integrity/confidentiality). According to Articles 13–15, it is necessary to provide transparent information to data subjects and grant rights of access, rectification and erasure, which apply where community platforms or DSOs process identifiable consumption data. Articles 25 and 32 mandate the privacy-by-design/by-default and security of processing, which is relevant for the architecture of FlexBIT’s digital solutions. The obligations for personal data breach notification are described thoroughly in Articles 33 and 34, which directly affect community platforms and service providers in case of cybersecurity incidents involving personal data. In concrete terms, this means that any energy-data architecture deployed by energy communities under FlexBIT must embed robust privacy and security safeguards and clearly allocate the roles of controllers and processors.

The Data Governance Act (DGA)^[39] deploys common rules for data intermediaries and data altruism and facilitates re-use of certain public-sector data. It proposes data intermediation services to be neutral and transparent, which may be relevant for platforms that mediate energy data between communities, Distribution System Operators (DSOs), Transmission System Operators (TSOs), and aggregators. It promotes frameworks for data altruism, expecting to support voluntary sharing of energy data for research, system planning or public-interest projects, provided that appropriate safeguards are in place. Although not energy-specific, the DGA provides tools for trusted data-sharing environments that FlexBIT can leverage when designing cross-actor data flows.

The Data Act^[7] is particularly relevant for access to and sharing data generated by connected devices and related services, including smart meters, home energy management systems, and IoT devices used by energy communities. It entitles users (including households, SMEs and communities) to access and share data generated by their devices and related services, dismantling contractual or technical barriers imposed by manufacturers or service providers. It establishes obligations for data holders to make such data available to users and third parties under fair, reasonable, and non-discriminatory (FRAND) terms. It includes provisions on business-to-government (B2G) data sharing in situations of exceptional need, and on cloud switching and interoperability, which are relevant when energy communities rely on cloud-based platforms (Figure 2.2). Although the Data Act Regulation has already entered into force, its main obligations have been applicable since September 2025 and are currently shaping the technical and contractual requirements for data access, portability, and interoperability that energy community platforms must comply with.

Figure 2.2: Lifecycle of energy data in digitally enabled energy communities and applicable EU legal instruments at each stage.

For the purposes of the FlexBIT project, the Data Act sets the regulatory framework to design architectures in which community members can authorise secure sharing of device and metering data to aggregators, DSOs or other services, subject to GDPR and cybersecurity safeguards.

The Digital Markets Act (DMA)^[21] focuses on large online platforms designated as gatekeepers and imposes obligations to avoid unfair practices and promote contestability. Article 6(10) demands gatekeepers to allow business users access to data generated by their activities on the platform, and to prohibit self-preferencing and tying/bundling practices that generate user lock-in. For energy communities, this is relevant in cases that they use or depend on large digital platforms (e.g. for IoT, cloud or market interfaces). The DMA ensures that communities and smaller service providers can access the data they generate and are not unfairly excluded from digital ecosystems that are critical for energy services.

Cybersecurity and system liability are regulated by the Directive on Security of Network and Information Systems (version 2) NIS2 Directive (EU) 2022/2555^[8] and the Network Code on Cybersecurity^[22]. NIS2 develops a horizontal framework for network and information security across critical sectors, including energy. It identifies essential and important entities, such as TSOs, DSOs and certain large energy-sector service providers, and imposes risk-management, incident-handling and reporting obligations. Management bodies approve and oversee cybersecurity measures, making cybersecurity a governance and liability issue at board level are required. It also mandates coordinated vulnerability disclosure and incident reporting, affecting how cyber incidents in energy-data infrastructures must be handled and communicated. Whereas most energy communities will not qualify themselves as essential entities, they will often rely on systems operated by entities that are in scope. Consequently, NIS2 indirectly sets the minimum cybersecurity expectations for community-facing platforms and services. The sector-specific Network Code on

Cybersecurity^[22] in electricity aligns with NIS2 Directive by defining concrete security requirements for cross-border electricity flows and system operation. It explains obligations for TSOs, DSOs and, where relevant, other market participants to conduct cyber-risk assessments, implement minimum security controls, and coordinate incident response. It defines roles and responsibilities for different actors while maintaining the cyber-resilience of the electricity system, including interfaces with third-party IT and OT providers (Figure 2.3).

Figure 2.3: Key EU legal requirements to technical design constraints and architectural choices in the FlexBIT framework.

From a FlexBIT perspective, the Network Code outlines how system liability and responsibility are distributed when cyber incidents affect grid operation or data exchange. Any architecture proposed by FlexBIT must therefore be compatible with these requirements and precisely allocate responsibilities between communities, platform operators, DSOs and other actors. Overall, these instruments develop a multi-layered legal environment in which energy communities are recognised as legitimate market actors with specific rights, but also operate within strict frameworks for data handling, cybersecurity and system liability. FlexBIT defines its role at this intersection, translating these high-level legal requirements into practical, interoperable and secure digital solutions that enable energy communities to participate safely and effectively in the European energy system.

The EU framework can be structured in three layers:

- a) Energy-market rights and participation rules (RED II/III, Electricity Directive/Regulation),
- b) Data governance and access rules (GDPR, Data Act, DGA, DMA), and
- c) Cybersecurity obligations (NIS2, Network Code on Cybersecurity).

FlexBIT sits at the intersection of these layers and translates them into operational requirements for interoperable architectures. Figure 2.4 depicts the FlexBIT legal framework.

Figure 2.4 FlexBIT legal framework

2.3 Key trends and Implementation changes

In part A and B of *The Future of European Competitiveness*, in 2024, it is analysed collectively a structural reform agenda aimed at restoring the EU's long-term competitiveness^[24, 25]. The documents emphasise to the central message, according to which Europe must radically modernise its governance, accelerate digital transformation, and reshape its markets to enable innovation, flexibility, and investment^[24, 25]. Several trends emerging from these analyses are directly relevant to the future of decentralised, digital energy systems and, therefore, strongly applicable to FlexBIT.

A shift toward a more agile and strategically coordinated EU governance model is considered necessary, as current governance structures are characterised by delayed procedures, fragmentation, and administrative complexity, all of which inhibit investment and innovation. According to the future of European competitiveness Part A: A competitiveness strategy for Europe^[24], there is need for refocusing EU institutions on fewer, mission-driven priorities, such as digitalisation, decarbonisation, and energy security. In part B of this report, the analysis also highlights the need to streamline and accelerate permitting, regulatory approvals, and the administrative processes that delay infrastructure deployment (including grids, digital infrastructure, and clean tech)^[25]. The report further proposes simplifying existing rules and reducing regulatory fragmentation as key measures to establish a more predictable and investment-friendly environment^[24]. The report calls for reinforced EU-level coordination in strategic sectors, such as energy, digital technologies, artificial intelligence, and grid development, where divergent national approaches have created significant inefficiencies. For FlexBIT project, this means that the transition to energy communities and digital energy markets must be embedded in a governance setting that prioritises interoperability, fast permitting, cross-border coordination, and simplified compliance obligations.

Regarding the acceleration of Europe's digital transformation as a competitiveness imperative, the reports identify digitalisation (e.g., AI, data infrastructures, high-capacity broadband, and cloud/edge computing) as the largest gap between Europe and global competitors. Key trends that are described in "The future of European competitiveness" Part B: In-depth analysis and recommendations^[25], and are relevant to FlexBIT are the underperformance of Europe's digital infrastructure, especially high-speed broadband and next-generation networks. Moreover, data is fragmented across sectors and Member States, creating a barrier to scaling digital services. It is eminent that the EU must rapidly develop secure, interoperable digital architectures, integrated cloud-edge systems, and shared data spaces.

In comparison with US and China, it is mentioned that AI adoption is significantly slower in the EU, and thus productivity and innovation are limited^[24]. Digital transformation is paramount for modernising traditional sectors, such as energy, industry, mobility, and making them competitive worldwide. These insights directly support FlexBIT's emphasis on digital interoperability, secure data exchange, and the development of a Digital Data Space for Energy Communities.

The development of more flexible, dynamic and innovation-friendly markets is also noted in *The Future of European Competitiveness*: part A and part B. Europe's markets are rigid, shaped by legacy rules that favour incumbents. They are fragmented, with differing national regulations limiting scalability and are insufficiently open to innovation, slowing adoption of new technologies^[24]. Key priorities to face these obstacles include the removal of barriers that prevent new entrants and local actors (including communities) from participating in energy and digital markets, the reformation of competition frameworks to enable rapid scaling of digital solutions, rather than restricting them prematurely, the support of integrated markets that can handle distributed assets, peer-to-peer trading, and decentralised flexibility, and the deployment of innovative businesses to transition from pilot scale to EU-wide deployment. All the above are closely aligned to FlexBIT's objectives, which are the establishment of an interoperable platform that allows communities, SMEs, households, and prosumers to participate in energy systems traditionally dominated by larger utilities.

The renewal of the EU energy system, aimed at strengthening security, affordability, and clean competitiveness, is outlined in the Energy chapter of *The Future of European Competitiveness: In-Depth*

Analysis and Recommendations (Part B)^[25]. This chapter describes Europe’s structural competitiveness gap, which is driven by high and volatile energy prices. In recent years, industrial electricity prices in the EU have been roughly two to three times higher than those in the United States, while natural gas prices have often been three to five times higher, creating significant cost pressures for energy-intensive sectors.), severe grid congestion, ageing infrastructure, and insufficient hosting capacity, slow and unpredictable permitting processes, limited long-term contracts and underdeveloped PPA markets, and insufficient digitalisation of energy networks. A faster roll-out of smart, digital grids supported by data-driven system management is proposed as one of major updates among other solutions such as leveraging decentralised actors (communities, SMEs, prosumers) to supply flexibility and support grids, modernising market design to reflect real-time constraints and integrate distributed assets, and enhancing cybersecurity and data governance across the energy value chain. These recommendations directly reinforce the rationale behind FlexBIT: energy communities and digital platforms can reduce local congestion, optimise self-consumption, and contribute to system flexibility and resilience.

Across all parts of the report “The Future of European Competitiveness (Part A & Part B)”, a continuous theme that emerges is the need for massive investment. A share equivalent to approximately 5% of EU GDP annually is used to deliver digitalisation, decarbonisation, defence, and competitiveness goals. According to the report, there is an urgent need to modernise State aid rules ensuring speed and simplicity, maturing capital markets to be capable of efficiently directing investments, implementing a European approach to financing strategic sectors, including digital infrastructures and energy networks, and reducing administrative complexity that deters private capital^[24].

This context is related to FlexBIT project in terms of investment in digital energy infrastructures, open data ecosystems, and cybersecurity and establishing a regulatory framework that reduces costs and complexity for communities and local actors.

A cross-cutting need for interoperability, security, and trusted data flows is also examined in all both parts A and B on The Future of European Competitiveness reports, in which is highlighted that Europe must build common, secure digital foundations for all strategic sectors. Core insights are data fragmentation weakens competitiveness and creates silos and the EU requirements for shared, interoperable data spaces with clear governance^[25].

Cybersecurity must be embedded across the fabric of digital energy systems while digital confidence is essential to participation by citizens and businesses. This strongly supports FlexBIT’s development of a GDPR-compliant, interoperable energy data space, the creation of secure APIs and digital interfaces for households, SMEs, DSOs, and aggregators, and a governance model fully aligned with the Data Governance Act and Data Act.

2.4 Financial instruments and support mechanisms

The development of Renewable Energy Communities (RECs), Citizen Energy Communities (CECs), and smart energy infrastructures relies not only on regulatory clarity but also on access to adequate and predictable financial support. Across the European Union, a combination of EU-level funding programmes (Horizon Europe, the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF), the Innovation Fund, and the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)), policy-driven financing tools such as the Innovation Fund, the Modernisation Fund, State-aid frameworks under the Climate, Energy and Environmental Aid Guidelines (CEEAG), and the European Investment Bank’s, and national support schemes (Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG) Support Scheme for Germany, Incentive Tariff for Renewable Energy Communities (Decree 414/2023) for Italy, *Energy Community Support Framework under Law 4513/2018 (amended by Law 5037/2023) for Greece and Renewable Energy Grants Scheme (RES Scheme by REWS) for Malta*, seeks to mobilise investment, lower the cost of capital, and ensure that local actors, including households, SMEs, cooperatives, and municipalities, can actively participate in the clean-energy transition. These instruments increasingly target not only renewable

generation but also digitalisation, data interoperability, flexibility services, storage solutions, and modern grid infrastructures, all of which are essential for the implementation of energy communities. Among EU-level financial instruments there is the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) & Cohesion Fund, which provides significant support to Member States for renewable energy deployment, energy efficiency, and smart grid upgrades. Under the 2021–2027 programming period, these funds explicitly prioritise the community-led renewable energy projects, the digitalisation of distribution networks, smart meters, data platforms, and local flexibility solutions and energy-poverty mitigation through community-based schemes. These funds are particularly important in regions with lower GDP per capita, where energy communities can perform as a vehicle for social inclusion and local economic development. Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) is currently the largest source of EU public investment in clean energy and digitalisation. Several national RRF plans include subsidies for collective self-consumption and energy-sharing infrastructures, accelerated permitting and grid modernisation measures, large-scale deployment of smart meters and digital substations, and financial incentives for citizen-led solar cooperatives. European Member States such as Italy, Greece, Spain, and Portugal have explicitly earmarked RRF resources for energy communities and local renewable generation. Horizon Europe funds research and innovation actions that support interoperable digital architectures, energy-data governance and cybersecurity, local flexibility markets and aggregation models, and pilot demonstrations of RECs/CECs with advanced digital tools. In addition, The Clean Energy Transition Partnership (CETP) complements this by co-funding applied R&I projects (including FlexBIT), enabling cross-border testing of energy-community solutions. InvestEU Programme provides guarantees and blended-finance instruments for community-scale renewable energy projects, energy storage and flexibility assets, digital and smart grid infrastructures and cooperative business models and municipal energy utilities. With the financial aid of the European Investment Bank (EIB), InvestEU supports projects that would otherwise face financing barriers due to size, risk, or innovative business models. European Investment Bank (EIB) has aligned its lending criteria with the EU Green Deal. These include smart grids and digital system management, distributed renewable energy, energy storage, and local energy markets, and electrification infrastructure. The EIB has also established dedicated facilities for citizen-led energy projects, aiming to reduce administrative burdens and improve access to finance for cooperatives and municipalities. Last, the LIFE Clean Energy Transition sub-programme supports capacity building for local authorities and communities, technical assistance for establishing RECs/CECs, and early-stage development services (feasibility studies, permitting, business models). It is especially relevant for regions with emerging community-energy ecosystems.

While EU-level instruments provide strategic direction and capital, national governmental instruments maintain primary responsibility for designing enabling frameworks for RECs and CECs. Member States implement a broad range of measures, including grants, feed-in tariffs, tax incentives, low-interest loans, guarantees, and dedicated technical assistance schemes. In Greece, there is National REC support schemes through the Development Law and Energy Community support window. RRF-funded programmes for rooftop PV, storage, and collective self-consumption. Special incentives for energy-poor households participating in RECs. Planned grid digitalisation and smart metering rollout to facilitate energy sharing. Italy has its own REC framework (in line with RED II/III) includes capital grants for renewable installations within communities, operational incentives for shared energy, strong RRF funding for smart grids, digitalisation, storage, and metering. The Italian market for energy communities, supported by stable remuneration schemes is one of the largest in EU. Germany demonstrates a dedicated funding for local energy initiatives and smart grid infrastructure via BMWK programmes. These programmes offer financial support for flexibility markets, demand-response integration, and digital grid upgrades. Strong ecosystems for cooperative models are supported by state-level development banks (e.g., KfW). Poland utilizes the EU Cohesion Policy funds directly towards digitalisation, renewable energy, and microgrid projects. National schemes supporting prosumers and cooperative renewables, though community frameworks are still evolving. Investments in CSIRE (national energy data hub) are intended to enable interoperable data flows. Malta deploys schemes for rooftop PV, small-scale storage, and energy efficiency upgrades. The Maltese initiatives focus on digitalisation and metering systems through national regulatory programmes while the

support for vulnerable customers and community-oriented renewable solutions is targeted. Smart grid and digital infrastructure are financed through dedicated national and EU mechanisms, supported by instruments such as the Connecting Europe Facility – Energy (CEF-Energy), the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), and the Modernisation Fund, all of which prioritise investments in grid digitalisation, smart metering, and advanced network technologies^[17]. Table 2.1 summarises the specific support measures and focuses areas adopted within the FlexBIT’s member states.

Table 2.1 Summary of specific support measures of the FlexBIT’ member states.

Member State	National Support Instruments and Schemes	Key Focus Areas and Digitalization Support
Greece	National REC support schemes via the Development Law and an Energy Community support window. National REC support schemes via the Development Law and an Energy Community support window	Special incentives are offered for energy-poor households participating in RECs. Support includes planned grid digitalisation and smart metering rollout to facilitate energy sharing.
Italy	REC framework established in line with RED II/III. Includes capital grants for renewable installations within communities. Offers operational incentives for shared energy.	Support is characterized by stable remuneration schemes. Strong RRF funding supports smart grids, digitalization, storage, and metering. The Italian market for energy communities is noted as one of the largest in the EU.
Germany	Dedicated funding via BMWK programmes. Support from state-level development banks (e.g., KfW).	Provides financial support for local energy initiatives and smart grid infrastructure. Programmes fund flexibility markets, demand-response integration, and digital grid upgrades. Maintains a strong ecosystem for cooperative models.
Poland	Utilizes EU Cohesion Policy funds. Features national schemes supporting prosumers and cooperative renewables.	Funds are directed towards digitalisation, renewable energy, and microgrid projects. Investments in CSIRE (the national energy data hub) are intended to enable interoperable data flows. Community frameworks are described as "still evolving"
Malta	Schemes for rooftop PV, small-scale storage, and energy efficiency upgrades. Utilizes dedicated national and EU mechanisms (including CEF-Energy, RRF, and the Modernisation Fund) for infrastructure financing.	Initiatives focus on digitalisation and metering systems through national regulatory programmes. Provides targeted support for vulnerable customers and community-oriented renewable solutions.

Beyond renewable deployment, the EU funding is progressively shifting towards a modernising distribution network that enables the full participation of local actors. Key examples include ERDF and RRF grants for smart transformers, digital substations, remote monitoring and automation, national DSOs receiving investment support for real-time data management systems and advanced metering infrastructure (AMI), Horizon Europe and CETP funding for cybersecurity-by-design and interoperable data spaces. These

mechanisms are fundamental to FlexBIT's objective of creating an interoperable, cyber-secure framework capable of integrating distributed energy resources, energy communities, and new digital market interfaces.

3 Review of Seperate Jurisdictions

3.1 Italy

3.1.1 Overview

Italy is widely acknowledged as a pioneer in the European energy transition, having achieved its 2020 renewable energy targets ahead of schedule in 2014. Currently, renewable sources account for 37% of the nation's electricity consumption, driven by a diverse mix of photovoltaic, hydroelectric, geothermal, and bioenergy technologies.

The Italian strategy for energy transition is anchored in decentralized renewable production, specifically through distributed generation and community-based frameworks. This approach prioritizes local participation and energy autonomy, with citizens positioned at the core of the transition. Energy communities in Italy are formally defined under two primary models: Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs). These legally structured entities empower collective self-consumption and energy sharing within defined geographic boundaries, supported by robust national legislation and the transposition of European directives.

Despite these advancements, Italy's energy profile presents a significant dichotomy. While the country is a market leader in clean technologies-contributing over 22% of photovoltaic panels integrated into European buildings and ranking among the top two EU producers of PV modules-its overall energy mix remains heavily reliant on fossil fuels. Fossil sources constitute 80% of the energy mix, significantly exceeding the European average of 69%, while clean energy sources cover only 20%, a figure that has slightly declined since 2020. This reliance is particularly acute in electricity generation, where fossil fuels account for 63.3%, compared to the EU average of 38.6%^[26].

The European Commission's 2025 assessment of Italy's National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) highlights urgent challenges to be addressed by 2030. Italy currently faces a gap in meeting EU climate targets, particularly within the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR) sectors (buildings, agriculture, transport, and waste). Current policies project only a 40.6% reduction in emissions by 2030, falling short of the required 43.7% target. Furthermore, the Land Use, Land Use-Change, and Forestry (LULUCF) sector has deteriorated by 13.2 Mt CO₂ eq. compared to the 2016-2018 baseline, with a projected gap of 9.2 Mt CO₂ eq. remaining by 2030^[27].

3.1.2 Key trends

The momentum in the development of energy communities has accelerated following the implementation of EU directives via Legislative Decrees No. 199^[28] and No. 210^[29] (November 2021). More recently, the regulatory landscape was expanded by the CACER Decree No. 414/2023^[30], which raised the capacity limit per installation from 200 kW to 1 MW and established a comprehensive three-tier incentive system.

Active community projects are proliferating across the country. Historical examples, such as the Cooperative Funes in Alto Adige (operational since 1921), demonstrate the long-term viability of community energy models. Contemporary digital pilots are advancing through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR)^[31]. The PNRR initially allocated €2.2 billion for energy communities in municipalities with fewer than 5,000 inhabitants. A significant policy shift occurred with the MASE decree of May 16, 2025^[27], which expanded eligibility to municipalities with fewer than 50,000 inhabitants (subject to EU Council approval). This expansion represents a critical evolution policy, dramatically widening the pool of potential beneficiaries.

Technologically, the nationwide rollout of second-generation smart meters and smart grid integration is enabling near real-time data access. This infrastructure is a prerequisite for advanced energy sharing mechanisms and the deployment of blockchain-based trading platforms.

Furthermore, the European Commission has approved a new €9.7 billion state aid scheme^[32] to support renewable electricity production. This scheme utilises transparent bidding procedures to procure 17.65 GW of capacity from onshore wind, solar photovoltaic, hydroelectric, and gas residue treatment plants. Concurrently, Italy has diversified its natural gas supply to reduce dependence on Russian imports, increasing the number of suppliers from 14 (2021) to 19 (2023), with Algeria now providing 37% of total imports^[33].

Despite these positive trends, energy poverty remains a critical issue linked to building performance. In 2023, 4.1% of the population reported difficulty paying energy bills, and 9.5% were unable to adequately heat their homes^[34]. To address this, energy communities are being integrated into the national monitoring system (National Statistical Program 2023-2025), ensuring that data is captured to inform national policy and verify contributions to renewable energy targets^[35].

3.1.3 Legal framework-barriers and opportunities

Italy demonstrates strong alignment with EU Directives through a comprehensive legislative architecture. The foundation is built on the full transposition of the Renewable Energy Directive II (RED II) via Legislative Decree No. 199/2021^[29] and the subsequent CACER Decree No. 414/2023^[29]. Crucially, the operational mechanics are defined by the TIAD (Testo Integrato Autoconsumo Diffuso)^[33], approved by ARERA Resolution 727/2022^[33]. This technical document regulates the "virtual" sharing model, allowing energy to be shared statistically rather than requiring physical private wires^[36]. The practical implementation of Italy's energy community framework is shaped by a combination of structural constraints and enabling mechanisms, which are summarised in [Table 3.1](#).

Table 3.1: Implementation barriers and enabling opportunities for renewable energy communities in Italy.

CATEGORY	ASPECT	DESCRIPTION
Implementation barriers	Geographic and grid constraints	Participation is limited to actors connected to the same primary HV/MV substation; substation boundaries are often not transparent to end-users despite recent transparency obligations.
	Corporate participation rules	Participation is restricted to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs); energy community activities cannot constitute the primary business activity of the entity.
	Permitting uncertainty	The identification of "suitable areas" under the Aree Idonee Decree is delegated to regional authorities, creating risks of regulatory fragmentation and delays ^[36] .
	Regional implementation timelines	Regions are granted up to 180 days to define specific "go/no-go" zones, potentially slowing permitting for ground-mounted installations.
	Technical and environmental compliance	New installations must generally comply with the additional capacity principle; DNSH compliance is mandatory for PNRR funding (e.g. hydrogen projects excluded above 3 tCO ₂ eq/t H ₂ ^[37]).
Opportunities	Simplified authorisation procedures	Renewable plants below 1 MW benefit from streamlined permitting and authorisation processes.
	Virtual energy sharing	The TIAD-based virtual sharing model enables energy sharing without the need for physical private networks or microgrids.

	Institutional support	The GSE provides a centralised portal for qualification procedures and technical guidance.
	Incentive layering	Regional support schemes can be combined with national incentives, enabling cumulative financial support.

These factors highlight the tension between a formally advanced regulatory framework and the operational challenges that continue to affect deployment at local and regional level. The European Commission’s 2024 assessment of Italy’s updated National Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) identifies critical gaps. The Commission noted that Italy has not sufficiently updated its Long-Term Renovation Strategy (LTRS) beyond 2020 benchmarks, lacking a targeted approach for the worst-performing buildings which directly impacts the efficiency of potential energy communities. Additionally, infrastructure bottlenecks persist, with interconnectivity levels remaining below EU targets, hindering the efficient dispatch of new renewable capacity^[38].

3.1.4 Alignment with cybersecurity and data protection rules

Italy has established a comprehensive cybersecurity framework tailored to the energy sector. The National Cybersecurity Perimeter Decree (No. 105/2019)^[39] mandates strict security measures for critical infrastructure, including ICT system screening, incident reporting within six hours, and certification requirements.

Compliance with the NIS2 Directive (Legislative Decree No. 65/2018)^[40] requires energy operators to implement robust risk assessment, notification protocols, and business continuity planning. Furthermore, ARERA Resolution 574/2019^[41] specifies cybersecurity standards for digital energy platforms, including annual compliance certification and penetration testing.

Regarding data privacy, the Open Data Decree (No. 200/2021)^[42] ensures that Distribution System Operators (DSOs) and data-sharing platforms comply with GDPR, facilitating secure energy data exchange while protecting user privacy.

3.1.5 Permit process

The permitting process for energy communities in Italy requires that the community first be legally established as a recognized entity under Legislative Decree 199/2021 and Legislative Decree 210/2021, which transpose the EU RED II Directive^[43]. Only after legal constitution can the community commission renewable energy installations^[44]. Applications for incentives must be submitted through the GSE portal within 120 days of commissioning, and projects must be fully operational within 18 months of approval^[44].

Key eligibility criteria for energy communities include:

- All generation units and consumption points must be connected to the same primary substation (HV/MV).
- Individual plants must have a nominal capacity of ≤ 1 MW to receive full incentives; for larger plants, only energy self-consumed by the community is eligible for incentives.
- Installations must comply with the “Do No Significant Harm” (DNSH) principle and must be new or substantially refurbished^[45].
- The commissioning date must be after the legal establishment of the community and after the entry into force of Legislative Decree 199/2021 (December 16, 2021).

Despite centralized oversight by GSE and the availability of online procedures, administrative practices vary between regions and municipalities. Some local authorities provide accelerated procedures for projects funded under the PNRR, but it remains the community’s responsibility to verify any additional regional rules and territorial constraints^[46, 47].

3.1.6 Status of the market

The Italian energy community market is currently navigating a pivotal transition from an experimental phase to structural maturity. While the landscape is historically anchored by long-standing cooperatives in northern regions (such as the distinct hydro-cooperatives of the Alps), the sector is witnessing a rapid bifurcation driven by recent legislative clarity.

As of early 2024, the market comprised approximately 154 operational Renewable Energy Communities (RECs)^[48], a figure that represents only a fraction of the estimated 400 projects currently in the pipeline^[49]. This momentum was significantly catalyzed by the operationalization of the GSE portal in April 2024, which finally unlocked the administrative pathway for mass adoption^[49]. The scale-up of energy communities in Italy is driven not only by legislative alignment but also by clearly defined capacity targets, dedicated public funding, and a standardised operational model, as summarised in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Market expansion targets and operational framework for energy communities in Italy.

DIMENSION	ELEMENT	DESCRIPTION
Capacity targets	National deployment goal	Target of 5 GW of installed capacity by 2027 under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR).
Public funding	Dedicated financial envelope	€2.2 billion allocated to support at least 2 GW of capacity in eligible municipalities.
	Eligibility threshold	Originally limited to municipalities with fewer than 5,000 inhabitants; recently expanded to 50,000 to broaden participation.
Operational framework	Energy-sharing model	Virtual sharing model defined under the Testo Integrato Autoconsumo Diffuso (TIAD).
	Settlement mechanism	Monthly financial settlement ^[43] managed by the Energy Services Manager (GSE), with members remaining connected to the public grid.

However, the market faces structural contradictions that threaten to reduce this acceleration. The EU's 2024 State of the Energy Union report highlights a paradox: while Italy is a top-tier manufacturer of renewable technologies, its energy system retains an excessive 80% dependence on fossil fuels^[50]. Systemic misalignments are evident in energy efficiency, where final energy consumption (101.70 Mtep) persistently exceeds the national target (93.05 Mtep), driven largely by an aging building stock. Furthermore, grid saturation in southern regions and lagging transport electrification, far behind the 2030 target of 4.3 million BEVs, pose significant integration challenges for new community generation^[33].

To bridge the gap between installed capacity and actual grid integration, the Ministry of Environment and Energy Security^[51] has launched a new statistical framework. Developed in collaboration with ISTAT, TERNA, GSE, ENEA, and ARERA, this initiative moves beyond simple capacity counting to capture granular, real-time data on consumption profiles and self-sufficiency ratios. This data is critical for validating the "social impact" requirements of RECs and optimizing future incentive mechanisms.

To address these gaps, the Ministry of Environment and Energy Security^[51] has implemented a new statistical framework in collaboration with ISTAT, TERNA, GSE, ENEA, and ARERA. This initiative aims to capture granular consumption and production data at the community level, essential for evaluating the effectiveness of incentives and optimizing national policy.

3.1.7 Financial incentives

Italy implements a structured three-tier incentive system for renewable energy communities (CERs), with premiums based on plant size and location. The premium tariff is calculated using the formula: $80 + \max(0; 180 - P_z)$ €/MWh, where P_z is the hourly zonal electricity price. This ensures a guaranteed top-up that

decreases as market prices rise^[43]. Regional adjustments further support development in areas with lower solar resources: central Italy receives an additional +4 €/MWh, while southern regions receive +10 €/MWh^[43]. Premium remuneration levels are differentiated by plant size to reflect economies of scale and cost structures, as summarised in [Table 3.3](#).

[Table 3.3: Capped premium tariff levels by plant size^{\[43\]}](#).

PLANT SIZE CATEGORY	INSTALLED CAPACITY RANGE	PREMIUM TARIFF CAP
Small plants	≤ 200 kW	120 €/MWh
Medium plants	200–600 kW	110 €/MWh
Large plants	> 600 kW	100 €/MWh

Capital contributions remain available for qualifying projects under the €2.2 billion PNRR allocation, covering up to 40% of eligible costs. In 2025, eligibility was expanded from municipalities with fewer than 5,000 inhabitants to all municipalities under 50,000 residents, significantly enlarging the pool of potential beneficiaries. Advance payments were increased from 10% to 30% of the total contribution to facilitate project implementation.

Premium tariffs are payable for 20 years from the plant’s commercial operation^[43]. Projects receiving capital contributions may see a proportional reduction in the tariff, except for public entities and local authorities^[44].

At the EU level, the European Commission approved a €9.7 billion state aid scheme under the Temporary Crisis and Transition Framework. Competitive auctions are planned to support 17.65 GW of new renewable capacity, including onshore wind, solar PV, small hydro, and biogas from wastewater. Aid is provided via 20-year Contracts-for-Difference (CfDs) covering approximately 95% of production, leaving 5% exposed to market risk. Small plants (≤1 MW) may access the scheme directly with administratively set prices. Projects must be operational within 36 months of award^[32].

3.1.8 Cost of implementation

Implementation costs in Italy are rigorously defined by the MASE Decree No. 414/2023, which establishes tiered maximum eligible investment costs to promote economies of scale. Communities in municipalities with fewer than 50,000 inhabitants can access a non-repayable PNRR capital grant covering up to 40% of these costs^[30]. The maximum recognized capital expenditure (CAPEX) limits are presented in [Table 3.4](#)^[44].

[Table 3.4: Maximum eligible CAPEX limits for renewable energy community projects in Italy.](#)

INSTALLED CAPACITY RANGE kW	MAXIMUM ELIGIBLE CAPEX (€ / kW)
< 20	1,500
20–200	1,200
200–600	1,100
> 600	1,050

Beyond the "hard costs" for hardware, project budgets must account for significant "soft costs" and operational requirements. Under the PNRR operational rules, expenses for feasibility studies, legal constitution, and technical project management are eligible for funding but are generally capped at 10% of the total eligible investment^[52]. Furthermore, ongoing operational expenditure (OPEX) must include mandatory annual fees for the GSE management portal, and the costs associated with "Do No Significant Harm" (DNSH) compliance, which requires specific environmental certifications for all components^[52].

3.1.9 Estimated profit margin

Profit margins in Italian energy communities are derived from a "revenue stack" comprising the Premium Tariff (Ti), the valorisation of shared energy (ARERA contributions), and the sale of excess energy to the grid. Authoritative market analysis by the Energy & Strategy Group (Politecnico di Milano) highlights three critical factors driving economic viability^[52](Table 3.5).

Table 3.5: Key profitability drivers for renewable energy communities in Italy.

PROFITABILITY DRIVER	MECHANISM	ECONOMIC EFFECT
Impact of public grants	40% non-repayable PNRR capital grant	Reduces payback period from approximately 8–10 years to 4–5 years
Tariff mechanism	Premium Tariff operating as a Contract for Difference (CfD)	Highest remuneration for plants ≤ 200 kW (capped at €120/MWh plus regional corrections); incentive decreases as the zonal electricity price (Pz) increases ^[27]
Self-sufficiency ratio	Maximisation of simultaneous local consumption	Higher value retention by avoiding grid purchases, outperforming feed-in remuneration alone

However, margins are legally constrained by social obligation requirements. Regulations mandate that the "economic benefit" of the incentive tariff, specifically the portion exceeding the share allocated to business members, cannot be treated as pure commercial profit. Instead, it must be directed toward social purposes or used to reduce the energy bills of residential members, limiting the returns extractable by private investors^[53]

3.2 Germany

3.2.1 Overview

Germany has established itself in the European energy transition, with energy communities playing an important role in achieving the country's climate targets. The German energy concept is built around the "Energiewende" (energy transition)^[54], which completed the phase-out of nuclear power in April 2023 and aims to achieve carbon neutrality by 2045. The share of renewable energies in the electricity sector has increased significantly in recent years and reached 54.4 percent in 2024, with wind and solar leading the expansion.

Germany has a long tradition of collectively organised energy supply and today hosts a broad spectrum of "energy cooperatives". In practice, most German initiatives fit the EU definition of REC under RED II. They are local, focus on renewable generation, and pursue environmental, social, and community benefits over profit^[55, 56]. Around 86% of German energy communities are primarily active in electricity generation (mainly photovoltaics and wind; heat often via biomass), with additional activities in distribution and, less frequently, grid operation (e.g., bioenergy villages, "Bioenergiedörfer")^[57].

Historically, electricity cooperatives ("Strom-Genossenschaften") supported rural electrification in the early 20th century. Since the mid-1990s, and especially between 2006 and 2013, grassroots activity surged: 890 energy cooperatives were founded in those years, many PV focused^[58]. This growth was catalysed by two reforms: (i) the Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG, 2000), which prioritised renewables and introduced fixed feed-in tariffs, and (ii) modernisation of cooperative law (Genossenschaftsrecht)^[59], which eased cooperative formation and ensured democratic governance. Growth slowed from 2013 due to reduced feed-in tariffs and the shift to competitive tenders from the EEG 2014/2017^[60, 61] reforms Frick et al., (2022)^[58].

As of roughly 2016, Germany had approximately 1,700 energy communities. Around 55% organised as cooperatives (largely PV) and about 37% as limited liability company structures (GmbH/UG & Co. KG), which commonly develop wind parks^[62]. Federal and EU law set the regulatory framework; the Federal Network Agency (Bundesnetzagentur, BNetzA) oversees implementation. Federal states are not the primary regulators; municipalities can be important partners (e.g., "Regionalwerke"), and green suppliers (e.g., Elektrizitätswerke Schönau) often cooperate on market and grid processes^[55].

In late 2025, through the amendments to the Energy Industry Act (EnWG) the energy sharing was implemented into national law. The paragraph 42c EnWG introduces the legal framework for energy sharing, transposing Article 15a of the EU's Internal Electricity Market Directive.

3.2.2 Key trends

The organisational and technological landscape of German energy cooperatives has undergone notable structural changes in the last decade. Since 2013, new formations have shifted from cooperatives to GmbH/UG & Co. KG, reflecting a transition from small PV projects (cooperative-led) to larger wind projects (often GmbH & Co. KG)^[62]. In urban communities, small projects more often use simple civil-law partnerships (GbR), while rural areas remain cooperative-heavy.

In terms of operational focus, approximately 86% of German energy cooperatives concentrate on electricity production, while roughly 100 communities operate their own grid (notably bioenergy villages) and about 150 operate grids and distribute heat/electricity without generating power themselves^[57].

Policy developments have significantly shaped market behaviour. The evolution of the Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG) from guaranteed feed-in tariffs to tenders^[60, 61] has altered the investments incentives and risk distribution within the sector. The 2023 amendments aim to re-accelerate deployment; small citizen projects may be exempted from tenders to lower entry barriers and uncertainty^[63, 64].

On November 13, 2025 the Bundesrat has approved the act on the amendment of energy industry Law to strengthen consumer protection in the energy sector. From June 2026 Energy communities become operational with the following provisions:

- End consumers can form energy communities to share renewable electricity via the public grid.
- Initially limited to participant within a single balancing area (*Bilanzierungsgebiet*) of one distributed system operator (DSO).
- From June 2028 it will be possible to extend the energy community area to members belonging to the adjacent balancing areas within the same control zone (TSO).

Digitalisation challenges further constrain in sector's evolution. The slow rollout of smart-meter and missing bidirectional metering options at DSOs hamper advanced community models^[55]. Government initiatives aim to accelerate digitisation^[65].

3.2.3 Legal framework-barriers and opportunities

Germany's framework blends EU directives (Electricity Market Directive; RED II) and national law^[59-61, 66]. While Germany recognises community concepts in policy design (e.g., actor diversity in tenders), it has not fully transposed all elements relevant to RECs/CECs—especially energy sharing^[66].

German energy communities imply several legal formas, each associated with different economic, governance, and risk policies. Cooperatives (Genossenschaften) constitute the most common form (~55% of communities), producing about 3.5% of Germany's renewable electricity. They feature democratic "one member, one vote" governance; average minimum investment is about €560, enabling broad participation with activities of PV (80%), distribution (36%) and wind (30%)^[67].

Limited liability structures (GmbH/UG & Co. KG) are prevalent in capital-intensive for wind projects due to higher capital needs; qualify as "citizen" entities when limited partners are private citizens.

Civil-law partnerships (GbR) continue to play a role in small projects; simple to form but entail personal liability^[62].

Starting in June 2026, energy communities will enter into operation under the following conditions. Final consumers will be allowed to establish energy communities for the purpose of sharing renewable electricity through the public distribution grid. In the initial phase, participation will be restricted to members located within a single balancing area (*Bilanzierungsgebiet*) served by one distribution system operator (DSO). As of June 2028, the geographical scope of energy communities may be expanded to include members from neighbouring balancing areas, provided they fall within the same transmission system operator (TSO) control zone. Energy communities are open to private individuals, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and municipalities and public institutions. Large corporations are explicitly excluded to maintain the citizen-focus character.

Participants must establish clear agreements covering electricity supply, billing, system operation, and maintenance. These operational tasks can be delegated to external service providers to ensure practical implementation. The shared electricity supplements rather than replaces existing energy supply contracts, meaning participants retain their original energy suppliers for residual consumption.

3.2.4 Alignment with cybersecurity and data protection rules

Energy communities must comply with the EU GDPR and Germany's Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG)^[68], applying privacy by design and limiting processing to operational needs. Where communities or their service providers fall under critical infrastructure thresholds, the IT Security Act 2.0 (IT SiG 2.0)^[69] and KRITIS^[70] obligations impose risk management, reporting, and resilience standards; NIS2 transposition will tighten these further for energy operators^[69].

Smart metering uses certified gateways and processes under the Metering Point Operation Act (MsbG), overseen by the Federal Office for Information Security (BSI). While rollout delays limit advanced use cases, the certified architecture sets a baseline for secure data exchange. Ongoing digitisation initiatives seek to streamline data flows between communities, DSOs, and market actors^[65, 69].

3.2.5 Permit process

The permitting and implementation pathway for German energy cooperatives depend on technology, size, and legal form, with federal rules implemented through DSOs and local authorities. At organisational level, communities must first determine their legal form (typically cooperative, GmbH/UG & Co. KG, or GbR). Each structure entails different governance and liability implications. Cooperatives ensure democratic control through GmbH/UG & Co. KG entities align voting with capital contributions while GbR exposes members to personal liability.

Cooperatives must also define membership criteria and territorial focus since most communities are local/regional by design. From a technical and regulatory standpoint Grid connection is applicable with the DSO (capacity check, metering concept, connection agreement). Cooperatives must also complete market registration with BNetzA when is needed and contract a balancing responsible party/retailer. Permitting obligations are differentiated by technology municipal building permits are required for most installations, whereas wind or biomass projects may trigger additional environmental assessments, species protection reviews, and sector-specific authorisations. District-heating or local heat-network projects may require concession agreements at municipal level. Digital-metering obligations apply depending on system size and classification; projects requiring certified smart-meter gateways must comply with data-protection and cybersecurity guidance issued by the Federal Office for Information Security (BSI) municipal building permits are required for most installations, whereas wind or biomass projects may trigger additional environmental assessments, species protection reviews, and sector-specific authorisations. In practical level, implementation challenges arise most noticeably in multi-apartment settings, where landlord-tenant electricity models or joint-self-supply schemes require complex internal wiring, metering, sub-meter allocation, and billing arrangements. Administrative timelines differ significantly between DSOs and regions, while larger projects may face extended processing periods. Early technical engagement with DSOs and municipal authorities is generally considered essential to reduce delays and ensure compliance^[55]. To establish Energy communities, the requirements that must be fulfilled are smart meters with 15-minute interval readings, renewable energy installations owned, leased, or rented by community members, and optional battery storage system, that can store only renewable energy.

3.2.6 Status of the market

Status of the market Germany's market is sizeable and diversified. Approximately 1,700 energy cooperatives (data related to year 2016) operate across technologies and roles^[62]. Cooperatives dominate by count and focus on PV; wind projects are frequently GmbH/UG & Co. KG. Cooperative membership is broad. Roughly 95% private individuals alongside banks, farmers, municipalities, public bodies, and churches; average minimum investment is modest (~€560), enabling inclusion^[67]. Co-ops account for about 3.5% of national renewable electricity^[67]

Activity spans in the following:

- Generation: 86% of communities (PV, wind; heat via biomass).
- Network operation: ~100 operate local grids (notably bioenergy villages).
- Heat/electricity distribution: ~150 operate grids and distribute without generation.
- Urban vs rural: Rural initiatives tend to form cooperatives; urban projects more often adopt GbR for small-scale deployments^[57]

Illustrative examples include Elektrizitätswerke Schönau (pioneer and multi-sector actor), BürgerEnergie Berlin (cooperative with broad civic remit), Bioenergiedorf Jühnde (local heat grid), and “Regionalwerke” (municipal consortia models).

3.2.7 Financial incentives

Germany has not yet introduced specific financial incentives such as premium or grid fee reductions comparable to Austria or Italy. Taxes, levies, and grid fees continue to apply through conventional residual electricity contracts. The Federal Network Agency retains discretion to establish future support mechanisms.

3.2.8 Cost of implementation

The cost of implementation for community energy projects in Germany reflects both the technological diversity of renewable energy systems and the administrative and digital requirements associated with operating within the national regulatory framework. Capital expenditure varies significantly across technologies, with rooftop photovoltaic (PV) installations generally representing the lowest entry point and onshore wind and biomass systems requiring substantially higher investment. However, community projects must also account for a wide range of soft costs, including legal formation, technical planning, permitting, metering, and ongoing compliance obligations. Digitalisation constitutes an additional cost layer, driven by mandatory certified smart metering infrastructure and cybersecurity requirements. Finally, labour and equipment capacity constraints, especially shortages of qualified installers and delays in metering infrastructure, can affect both timelines and total project costs^[55] (Table 3.6).

Table 3.6: Cost Components for Implementing Community Energy Projects in Germany

CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	TYPICAL COST RANGE
Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)	Rooftop PV installations	€1,000–1,700 per kWp
	Ground-mounted PV	€800–1,200 per kWp
	Onshore wind	€1.3–2.2 million per MW
	Biogas/biomass heat systems	€3,000–5,000 per kWth/e
Soft Costs & Compliance	Legal entity formation, advisory services, technical design, permitting procedures (particularly for MW-scale projects)	Project-dependent; moderate to high administrative burden
	Metering configuration, IT setup, audits, and insurance	Variable; recurring operational cost
	Grid-connection fees (DSO-provided estimates)	From a few thousand euros for small PV systems to substantially higher costs for MW-scale projects requiring grid reinforcement
Digitalisation requirements	Certified smart meters and gateways for each connection point	Unit-based cost; varies by device and installer availability

	Community energy management platforms; cybersecurity & GDPR compliance	Project-dependent; medium to high integration cost
Capacity constraints	Shortages of certified installers and delays in metering infrastructure	Not a direct cost category, but contributes to increased project timelines and higher soft-cost expenditure

3.2.9 Estimated profit margin

Returns vary by technology, scale, support scheme, and risk management. As a rule of thumb, cooperative projects target modest, stable, single-digit returns:

- PV cooperatives: often low to mid-single-digit IRR (e.g., ~3–5%) under tariff/auction backed revenues.
- Onshore wind community projects: potentially mid-single-digit IRR (e.g., ~5–7%) in favourable locations with robust wind yield.
- Incremental revenues from retailing to members, flexibility services, and heat sales can enhance margins, but depend on local regulation and digital capabilities.

Key sensitivities include auction outcomes, grid costs, metering/IT requirements, installer availability, and policy changes. Long-term performance improves with professional management, reserve funds for repowering/repairs, and partnerships with experienced suppliers. Beyond financial metrics, communities deliver socio-economic value: participation, local acceptance, regional value creation, and contributions to decentralisation and energy security^[57, 71].

3.3 Malta

3.3.1 Overview

Malta’s energy concept is centred on improving security of supply, integrating renewable sources, and enhancing consumer participation in the energy market. The Low Carbon Development Strategy (2021) and National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) 2021–2030 highlight efforts to decarbonise and electrify the economy, but energy communities are not yet a structured part of national energy policy. Although Malta has transposed core elements of RED II and Directive 2019/944, including consumer empowerment and collective self-consumption provisions, there is no dedicated national law establishing Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) or Citizen Energy Communities (CECs). Progress has focused more on rooftop PV deployment and individual self-consumption schemes rather than community-based initiatives.

3.3.2 Key trends

Malta is taking initial steps to enable energy sharing and digital energy services through smart grid upgrades and regulatory sandbox projects. The Energy and Water Agency (EWA) has conducted pilots under the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan and with the EU-funded SCORE and REACT projects, which explored energy cooperation among households. The launch of the Smart Utilities Metering Infrastructure by ARMS Ltd. supports two-way metering and facilitates future energy communities. However, no operational RECs or CECs exist to date, and legislative tools remain underdeveloped, with reforms currently under consultation.

3.3.3 Legal framework-barriers and opportunities

Malta has transposed key provisions of RED II and Directive 2019/944 via subsidiary legislation under the Electricity Market Regulations (S.L. 545.34)^[72] and amendments to the Energy and Water Services Act (Cap.

545)^[73]. However, these do not fully define RECs or CECs as distinct legal entities with dedicated rights. There are no provisions for proximity requirements, energy sharing rights, or consumer-centric governance models. Furthermore, while collective self-consumption is technically feasible, no regulatory path exists to support shared ownership models or flexible grid participation. Legal and administrative uncertainty, especially small actors, hinders full compliance with EU obligations.

3.3.4 Alignment with cybersecurity and data protection rules

Malta fully enforces the GDPR through the Data Protection Act (Cap. 586)^[74], with the Office of the Information and Data Protection Commissioner (IDPC) overseeing compliance. The NIS2 Directive has not yet been fully transposed but is expected to expand obligations for energy sector actors, particularly Enemalta plc and ARMS Ltd., which act as DSO and metering/data services providers. There is currently no data governance model specific to energy communities. While smart meter data is handled under GDPR-compliant systems, broader data-sharing, interoperability, and cybersecurity requirements under the upcoming Data Act and NIS2 remain unaddressed in the energy community context.

3.3.5 Permit process

No specific permitting regime exists for RECs or CECs in Malta. Renewable energy installations, including PV systems, are subject to existing Development Planning Regulations (L.N. 14.0 of 2016)^[75] and grid connection procedures under Enemalta's guidelines. While small-scale PV systems (up to 16A per phase) benefit from simplified processes, collective or community-based systems lack tailored procedures. Applicants face technical, legal, and administrative challenges, particularly in multi-tenant buildings or cooperatives. The absence of a recognised legal status for energy communities prevents streamlined licensing or interconnection pathways under the Electricity Market Regulations.

3.3.6 Status of the market

As of mid-2025, Malta does not have any formally recognised Renewable Energy Communities or Citizen Energy Communities. Existing support schemes focus on individual prosumers through feed-in tariffs and capital grants. The Smart PV Grant Scheme and Solar Rights for Condominiums initiatives aim to expand access but fall short of enabling structured community models. Although community energy has been mentioned in recent public consultations, no functioning energy sharing project has yet emerged. The lack of regulatory clarity and legal basis is a significant limiting factor for market entry.

3.3.7 Financial incentives

Financial support in Malta is primarily aimed at individual renewable installations rather than collective energy communities. The Malta Sustainable Energy and Water Conservation Unit offers grants of up to €3,000 for residential PV installations and tax credits for energy efficiency upgrades. Net metering and feed-in tariffs (fixed at €0.15–€0.17/kWh for 20 years) are available to households but not designed for RECs or CECs. The Investment Aid for Energy Efficiency Measures scheme under Malta Enterprise supports SMEs, but collective ownership or community-based projects do not qualify unless structured as a company or cooperative under standard commercial law.

3.3.8 Cost of implementation

Capital costs for small-scale PV range from €1,200 to €1,500 per kWp, with additional administrative and legal costs for setting up cooperatives or partnerships. For future RECs or CECs, implementation would also require legal consultancy for entity formation (estimated €1,500–€3,000), compliance with data handling requirements, and metering infrastructure adaptation. Given the lack of support structures or advisory

platforms, initial costs for community-driven initiatives are likely to exceed those for individual prosumers. Regulatory uncertainty increases perceived risk, deterring investment at scale.

3.3.9 Estimated profit margin

Under current frameworks, individual PV prosumers in Malta see payback periods of 6–8 years, with internal rates of return between 6% and 10% depending on system size and usage. In a hypothetical REC/CEC scenario, shared operational and administrative costs would reduce individual margins unless additional incentives or regulatory facilitation were introduced. Profitability is constrained by the absence of dynamic tariffs, energy sharing rights, and aggregation mechanisms. Without legislative reform, community energy remains marginal in terms of economic viability.

3.4 Poland

3.4.1 Overview

Poland largely aligns with the evolving EU regulatory framework on energy communities. In recent years, EU policy has increasingly promoted the active involvement of citizens in the energy transition, recognising energy communities as an effective instrument for collective participation in energy production, consumption, and management. Within this context, the concept has gained growing visibility in Poland, particularly following the transposition of recent EU directives and the introduction of related national reforms.

The foundation for energy communities in the EU lies in two key pieces of legislation. Firstly, the Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944, which introduced the concept of Citizen Energy Communities. Secondly, the Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001, later updated by RED III, which defined Renewable Energy Communities. These directives require all EU member states, including Poland, to create legal and regulatory frameworks that allow such communities to flourish. The objective is to enable citizens not only to consume energy, but also to generate, store, and sell it, primarily through renewable sources such as solar and wind energy.

Poland has been intensifying its energy transition efforts for several years, implementing legislative solutions to enable the development of energy communities, including energy cooperatives, energy clusters and, more recently, citizen energy communities (CEAs). The key pieces of legislation in this regard are the Law of February 20, 2015, on Renewable Energy Sources (the so-called RES Law)^[76], the Law of April 10, 1997. - Energy Law^[77], as well as the Law of September 16, 1982. - Cooperative Law. Amendments to these acts are aimed at bringing national law in line with EU directives, including Directive 2018/2001 (RED II) and Directive 2019/944.

Poland responded to this call by amending its Energy Law in September 2023^[78] and updating the Renewable Energy Sources Act. These changes formally recognized energy communities and laid out the rules for their operation. The reforms also aligned with Poland's broader climate commitments, including targets set in its National Energy and Climate Plan to increase the share of renewables in the energy mix to over 26% by 2025 and more than 29.8% by 2030.

3.4.2 Key trends

In recent years, Poland has introduced a legal and institutional framework that enables the development of energy community initiatives, primarily through the transposition of EU energy directives and targeted national reforms. Within this framework, a limited but growing number of pilot projects have emerged, illustrating how collective energy schemes can operate in practice, particularly at municipal level, and how they may contribute to local energy management, cost reduction, and increased use of renewable generation.

Under the new regulations, energy communities in Poland now enjoy a range of rights and opportunities. They can access the energy grid under fair conditions, participate in energy markets, and benefit from support schemes funded by the EU, such as the LIFE Programme and the Social Climate Fund. Local governments are also encouraged to collaborate with communities, especially in projects involving solar energy and energy sharing in residential buildings.

One of the most dynamic recent examples comes from the border region of Zgorzelec in Lower Silesia. There, local authorities and community partners joined forces to establish the Zgorzelec–Gmina Energy Cooperative, an initiative designed to accelerate the area’s transition toward renewable energy. The cooperative primarily develops solar generation assets and supplies clean electricity to municipal facilities and participating residents, contributing to improved local energy security and greater stability of long-term energy costs. By combining local ownership with coordinated leadership from the public sector, this strategic approach has positioned Zgorzelec as a regional frontrunner in community-based energy transformation. The model, rooted in collective responsibility and practical deployment of renewable technologies, has already drawn attention from neighbouring municipalities exploring similar cooperative frameworks.

Until recently, Poland’s regulatory framework for energy cooperatives was relatively restrictive, allowing such initiatives to operate only within up to three neighbouring rural or mixed rural–urban municipalities. This limitation constrained not only their geographic scope but also their ability to expand into more densely populated areas, where demand for local and community-based energy solutions is increasing rapidly. A forthcoming legislative reform alters this situation. Under the revised framework, the distinction based on the “type” of municipality is removed, enabling fully urban municipalities (gminas, the basic level of local government in Poland) to establish energy cooperatives for the first time. The territorial requirement remains unchanged, as cooperatives will continue to operate within one to three adjacent municipalities, irrespective of whether they are rural, urban, or mixed. The reform is expected to enter into force by the end of 2025 and represents a significant step toward scaling community-based energy models across Poland’s diverse municipal landscape.

In 2024, a major milestone was reached with the formation of Związek SERC, a national coalition uniting ten energy cooperatives. This alliance advocates for better legal frameworks, shares best practices, and works to ensure that EU energy community directives are fully implemented in Polish law. It represents a shift from isolated projects to a coordinated national movement.

The practical impact of these changes is already visible. Across Poland, communities are launching collective solar installations, setting up local energy cooperatives, and even creating their own energy suppliers to offer stable prices to members. Events like the European Energy Communities Forum 2025 in Kraków have showcased these initiatives, highlighting how grassroots efforts are reshaping the energy landscape.

In the Polish model of energy communities, a special role is played by energy cooperatives, which can operate mainly in rural and urban-rural areas, and soon also in urban municipalities as the amended regulations come into force. A key feature of this model is localism, i.e. limiting operations to the area of one distribution system operator and a specific group of municipalities. Cooperatives can engage in the generation of electricity, heat or biogas from RES, and the balancing of these needs exclusively for the benefit of members.

A registry of citizen energy communities was also introduced in 2024, which formalises the existence of such entities and allows them to operate in accordance with national law. Poland has also established a register of energy clusters and a list of aggregators. Despite progressive legislative efforts, challenges remain in the practical implementation of the legislation, simplifying administrative procedures and ensuring market access for smaller entities.

3.4.3 Legal framework-barriers and opportunities

The Polish legal system regulates the activities of energy cooperatives through several concurrent legal regimes. Energy cooperatives operate under the Renewable Energy Sources Act of 2015, as well as the provisions of the Cooperative Law and the Law on Farmers' Cooperatives. Their activities are territorially limited to the area of rural or urban-rural municipalities (soon also in urban municipalities), with a maximum limit of 1,000 members (Article 38e of the RES Law)^[76]. These entities are authorised to generate, consume and balance electricity, heat or biogas for their own use.

Energy clusters, according to Article 2(15a) of the RES Law^[76], are voluntary agreements of local government units, businesses and local communities, operating in a limited area. Citizen energy communities, on the other hand, as a novelty introduced in the Energy Law (Article 11zn-11zo)^[77], are a structure modelled on Directive 2019/944 and can perform a wide range of energy activities, but with significant subject and functional limitations.

Despite formal recognition of these entities, barriers remain significant. These include the lack of a unified energy billing system between community members (no framework for energy sharing), insufficient simplified procedures for micro-installations and communities, restrictions on access to commercial balancing systems, and the lack of clear dispute resolution mechanisms. These impediments affect the real opportunities for smaller entities to operate and to cooperate with DSO.

Despite growing enthusiasm for energy communities in Poland, several legal and administrative challenges continue to hinder their development. One of the most significant issues is the incomplete transposition of EU directives into national law. While Poland has made strides in aligning with the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II/III) and the Electricity Market Directive, gaps remain. These gaps create uncertainty around the legal status and rights of energy communities, making it difficult for new initiatives to navigate the system confidently.

Another major obstacle is the complexity of administrative procedures. Establishing an energy community often involves navigating a maze of registration requirements, licensing protocols, and compliance checks. For small municipalities, these bureaucratic demands can be overwhelming and discouraging.

Financial regulations also pose a challenge. Energy communities, which are typically small and community-driven, face disproportionate financial and accounting obligations. These requirements, which were primarily designed with larger commercial entities in mind, can place a disproportionate burden on the limited administrative and financial resources of local cooperatives and associations.

Access to the energy grid is another persistent issue. Many communities, especially in rural areas, struggle with outdated infrastructure and limited grid flexibility, making it difficult to connect renewable energy sources or implement local balancing mechanisms. Finally, limited awareness and insufficient institutional support mean that many potential energy community leaders, whether citizens or local authorities, remain unaware of the legal opportunities available to them or lack the practical guidance required to initiate such initiatives.

Despite these challenges, the legal landscape in Poland also offers promising opportunities for energy communities. In 2018, reforms updated the legal definitions of both energy clusters and energy cooperatives, clarifying their functions, governance requirements, and territorial limitations. These adjustments strengthened the framework for local energy initiatives and supported the development of community-driven renewable energy projects. Since 2023, national legislation has formally recognized energy communities, allowing them to operate under various legal forms such as energy cooperatives, clusters, and associations. This recognition provides a foundation for participation in the energy market and access to support mechanisms.

One of the most significant opportunities lies in funding availability. Energy communities can now tap into a range of EU and national financial instruments, including the LIFE Programme and the Social Climate Fund. These resources support renewable energy generation, energy efficiency improvements, and infrastructure upgrades, making community-led projects more viable and scalable.

Poland's National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) further strengthens the case for energy communities. With ambitious targets to increase the share of renewables to over 26% by 2025 and 29.8% by 2030, energy communities are positioned as key contributors to national climate goals. Their decentralized nature and local engagement make them ideal partners in achieving these targets.

Moreover, the legal framework offers flexibility in organizational structure, allowing communities to choose models that best suit their needs, whether it's a cooperative in a small town, a tenant-led solar initiative in an apartment block, or a district-level energy-sharing scheme in a city. This adaptability encourages innovation and inclusivity.

Finally, there is a growing wave of political and public support for energy communities. As Poland seeks to reduce its dependence on fossil fuels and enhance energy security, community-led energy solutions are increasingly seen as strategic assets. This shift in perception is helping to build momentum and legitimacy for energy communities across the country.

3.4.4 Alignment with cybersecurity and data protection rules

Poland has fully implemented the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (RODO)^[79], as well as national legislation on critical infrastructure protection. However, regulations relating directly to civic energy and energy communities are still fragmented.

In the context of the digitisation of the energy sector and compliance with European initiatives such as NIS2 (the Network and Information Security Directive), the Data Governance Act (EU Regulation 2022/868) and the proposed Data Act, there is a lack of dedicated legislation regulating cyber security for energy cooperatives and communities. Metering systems, smart meters or aggregation platforms, which are beginning to be introduced, lack consistent oversight in terms of data security or system integrity.

The role of the Energy Regulatory Authority (ERO) is mainly focused on formal and regulatory aspects, while the lack of a central authority overseeing the IT area for energy communities limits the ability to respond to digital incidents. Responsibility for data and its processing remains with the operators and members of the communities, which can result in a lack of clear interoperability standards.

In addition, an important element in the development of digital security and data management will be the launch of the Central Energy Market Information System (CSIRE), which will be operated by the Polish Power Grid as the Energy Market Information Operator (OIRE). CSIRE is to serve as an open energy market data platform, and its implementation will enable, among other things, dynamic tariffs and personalisation of offers to consumers. OIRE's main tasks will be to administer CSIRE, develop Standards for Information Exchange (SWI), and oversee data security and access.

For energy communities, the use of CSIRE will imply the need to meet certain requirements for access management, authorisation control and compliance with regulations on the processing of personal data. It is important to recognise that the implementation of CSIRE will be crucial to the further digital transformation of energy communities and their integration into the national electricity system.

As energy communities in Poland become more digitally integrated, the need to align their operations with cybersecurity and data protection regulations has grown significantly. In 2025, this alignment is no longer optional as it has become essential for building trust, ensuring resilience, and complying with both national and EU laws.

On the cybersecurity front, Poland has adopted the EU's NIS2 Directive, which strengthens the security of network and information systems across critical sectors, including energy. This means that even small, community-led energy initiatives must now consider how they protect their digital infrastructure. From smart meters and solar inverters to energy-sharing platforms, these systems are increasingly interconnected and vulnerable to cyber threats. As a result, energy communities are expected to implement risk management strategies, establish incident reporting protocols, and ensure their systems meet minimum cybersecurity

standards. While not all communities have the resources for a full-time cybersecurity officer, many are turning to external experts or shared services to meet these obligations.

At the same time, the processing of personal data, particularly energy consumption data collected through smart technologies, brings energy communities within the scope of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). This regulation requires transparency in how data is collected and used, limits data collection to what is strictly necessary, and mandates strong safeguards against data breaches. Community members must be informed of their rights, including the ability to access, correct, or delete their personal data. For many energy communities, this has meant developing clear data governance policies, conducting Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs), and, in some cases, appointing a Data Protection Officer (DPO).

The Polish government is actively working to harmonize energy regulations with these digital requirements. Recent amendments to energy law include references to cybersecurity and data protection, and national agencies are beginning to offer training and guidance tailored to community energy projects. There is also increasing emphasis on the adoption of secure-by-design technologies, whereby systems are developed from the outset with privacy and security considerations embedded into their architecture.

In this evolving landscape, energy communities are learning that digital responsibility is just as important as environmental sustainability. By aligning with cybersecurity and data protection rules, they not only comply with the law but also strengthen the trust of their members and the resilience of their systems.

3.4.5 Permit process

In Poland, the procedure for obtaining permits for energy communities varies depending on their organizational form. In the case of energy cooperatives, it is required to meet the requirements under the Law on Renewable Energy Sources (Article 38c-38k)^[76], the Law - Cooperative Law^[80], and in addition - registration with the National Center for Agricultural Support (NEB). A condition for registration is, among other things, documenting that the cooperative's total installed capacity of RES does not exceed 10 MW, and that its members are connected to the same distribution network with a voltage lower than 110 kV.

The process of establishing a cooperative requires gathering at least 10 natural persons or three legal entities, drafting a charter, registering with the National Court Register, preparing an investment plan and reporting the activity to the NEB. Despite the clear legal basis, the procedures are complex and require legal and technical support. In practice, they are a significant barrier for small communities without adequate expertise. As of July 2025, the list counts 287^[81] energy co-ops.

For citizen energy communities (OSEs), as defined in the Energy Law (Article 11zn-11zm)^[77], registration in the OSE Register maintained by the President of the ERO is mandatory. Registration requires identification of members, scope of activities, location and infrastructure, and provision of evidence of compliance with the criteria provided for in Directive 2019/944. As of December 2025^[82], only one citizen energy community is registered. For energy clusters, registration is voluntary but increasingly required when applying for public funding. As of December 2025, 12^[83] clusters out of about 100 operating in Poland were registered.

When CSIRE is launched, planned for 2025, energy communities will be required to use digital forms and integrated processes for handling market data, which could significantly simplify or, if unprepared, complicate the permitting process. OIRE will also be responsible for verifying the completeness and integrity of the data, which means that communities will be required to integrate it fully and in accordance with the platform.

In Poland, the procedures for licensing and connecting Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) to the grid are still considered complex and burdensome, despite recent legal reforms aimed at simplifying them.

While the Polish legal framework has begun to incorporate EU directives, such as the Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 and the Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001 (RED II), many energy communities report that the administrative processes remain opaque and costly. Licensing and registration procedures, particularly for energy sharing and grid connection, often lack transparency and do not follow predictable timelines. This can discourage smaller communities or grassroots initiatives from pursuing renewable energy projects.

Moreover, the grid connection process itself poses technical and regulatory challenges. Distribution System Operators (DSOs) are required to cooperate with energy communities, but in practice, this cooperation can be inconsistent. Communities frequently face delays, unclear requirements, and high connection fees, especially when trying to integrate decentralized energy sources like solar or biogas into the existing grid.

Efforts are underway to streamline these procedures, guided by EU recommendations to simplify permit-granting and facilitate Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs). However, full implementation in Poland is still in progress. The Energy Community Secretariat and other EU bodies continue to push for fair, proportionate, and transparent procedures, emphasizing the need to remove unjustified regulatory barriers and ensure non-discriminatory treatment of energy communities as legitimate market actors.

In summary, while the legal framework in Poland is evolving to support energy communities, the licensing and grid connection processes remain complex, and further reforms are needed to make them truly accessible and efficient.

3.4.6 Status of the market

The market for energy communities in Poland is still at an early stage of development. According to data collected by the ERO and the Ministry of Agriculture, several dozen actively operating energy cooperatives have been registered by 2024, a significant number of which are pilot projects implemented under the RENALDO project. Most such initiatives are being established in rural areas, where it is possible to take advantage of support programs for RES development and local electricity infrastructure.

Interest in local communities is growing, but their activity is constrained by several barriers from unclear regulations on internal settlements to the lack of mechanisms to guarantee the profitability of investments. There is also a lack of systemic technical and organizational support that would enable, for example, the creation of virtual power plants or the use of group balancing.

In the coming years, a key factor shaping the market for energy communities will be the implementation of the CSIRE system, which will define new mechanisms for the participation of entities in the energy market. The system is to serve as a central platform for collecting, processing and sharing energy market data. Participation in CSIRE will be mandatory for all sellers, distributors and generation entities, as well as for energy communities. Integration with CSIRE will give communities access to metering data, facilitate billing and enable access to new services such as dynamic tariffs, balancing services or integration with aggregators.

The energy clusters in operation are characterized by great diversity, ranging from consultative agreements to formal structures with active operations. Despite the registry of energy clusters, there is no comprehensive database covering their operational status, scale of activity and actual impact on local power systems.

In the case of aggregators, the market is only just taking shape. The July 2023 law defined the framework for aggregators' activities and launched the List of Aggregators maintained by the ERO President. This is a step towards the development of flexibility services and modern demand-side management, but as of today their market presence is marginal.

As of 2025, the presence of fully functioning Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) in Poland is still limited but growing, with several pilot projects and early-stage initiatives paving the way for broader adoption.

While Poland has legally recognised energy communities and begun aligning with EU directives, the actual number of operational RECs and CECs remains small. Most existing initiatives are still in the pilot or development phase, often supported by EU funding or local government partnerships. These projects typically focus on solar energy generation, energy sharing within housing cooperatives, or municipal energy cooperatives.

Despite these efforts, energy sharing mechanisms, which are a core feature of RECs and CECs, are still not widely implemented in practice. Legal and technical barriers, such as complex grid connection procedures and lack of standardised energy settlement systems, continue to slow down the rollout of fully functional energy communities.

In summary, while Poland has laid the legal groundwork and launched several promising initiatives, the actual presence of mature, fully operational RECs and CECs is still emerging. The coming years will be crucial for scaling up these models and integrating them more deeply into the national energy system.

3.4.7 Financial incentives

Poland offers a variety of financial instruments to support the development of energy communities, but their availability and effectiveness vary. Energy cooperatives can benefit from a system of discounts, which allows them to store energy in the grid and receive it at a ratio of 1:0.6, which means a significant reduction in the cost of purchasing energy (Article 38c of the RES Act)^[76]. In addition, cooperatives enjoy an exemption from the RES fee, power fee and excise tax, if the capacity of the installation does not exceed 1 MW.

Both cooperatives and clusters and OSEs can also apply for investment support under programs of the National Environmental Protection and Water Management Fund (e.g., Energy Plus, My Electricity for Communities), as well as funds from the National Recovery Plan and EU funds for 2021-2027. Funding includes, among other things, the purchase and installation of RES installations, energy storage systems, IT infrastructure and educational activities.

A novelty is the support dedicated to energy communities under regional programs, including funds managed by provincial governments. The condition for obtaining support is often having a legal form registered in the relevant register (e.g., the National Court Register, the OSE Register or KOWR Register), which motivates the formalization of activities.

Despite the availability of financial tools, their use is relatively low. The reasons are complex application procedures, short duration of calls, lack of continuity of support and insufficient promotion of available funding sources. As a result, many initiatives remain at the conceptual stage, without being translated into real investments.

In the context of regulatory incentives, the Energy Market Information Operator (EMIRE) also envisions new tariff models (e.g., dynamic tariffs) available to entities operating in collective self-consumption models and local energy markets as a potential benefit for active communities. However, the realisation of these opportunities will depend on the full implementation of CSIRE and active community participation in the system.

In 2025, Poland offers a growing but still developing set of incentives for energy communities. These include grants, tax reliefs, and net billing schemes, aimed at encouraging local renewable energy production and community-led projects.

Energy communities can apply for cash grants that may cover up to 100% of eligible costs, especially if the project aligns with regional development goals or environmental priorities. Through the Polish Investment

Zone, they may also qualify for income tax exemptions, particularly if they invest in renewable infrastructure or energy storage.

While traditional feed-in tariffs are no longer in use, communities benefit from net billing, where surplus energy fed into the grid is credited and used to offset future consumption. Additionally, EU programs like the LIFE Programme and the Social Climate Fund offer financial support for energy efficiency and renewable energy initiatives.

Though promising, these incentives often require navigating complex application processes, which can be a barrier for smaller or less experienced groups.

3.4.8 Cost of implementation

Establishing an energy community in Poland in 2025 is a promising but resource-intensive endeavor. While the legal framework is gradually becoming more supportive, the capital and administrative costs involved remain a significant hurdle for many aspiring communities.

From a financial perspective, the initial capital investment required to establish a small- to medium-sized energy community, typically centred on solar installations, can range from approximately EUR 115,000 to well over EUR 700,000. (approximately PLN 500,000 to several million PLN). These costs cover not only the purchase and installation of renewable energy technologies like photovoltaic panels, inverters, and batteries, but also the necessary infrastructure for grid connection and digital energy management systems. For communities aiming to include energy storage or smart metering, the costs can rise even further.

Beyond the physical infrastructure, there are substantial administrative costs. Setting up an energy community involves navigating a complex web of legal and regulatory requirements. This includes registering the entity, obtaining licenses, ensuring compliance with energy market rules, and meeting data protection and cybersecurity obligations. These processes often require legal and technical expertise, which adds to the overall cost, especially for smaller, volunteer-led initiatives. Although support tools remain limited, some helpful resources do exist. One example is the RENALDO Calculator, developed under the project "RENALDO" commissioned by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. This free, publicly accessible tool enables users to estimate the technical and financial parameters of prospective energy cooperatives, including their energy balance and potential economic benefits, providing much-needed guidance for communities considering such initiatives.

Studies and pilot projects have shown that these transaction and coordination costs are among the main reasons why many potential energy communities in Poland remain at the planning stage. While grants and tax incentives can help offset some of the financial burden, the upfront complexity and cost of launching a community energy project still pose a barrier to widespread adoption.

The costs associated with setting up and running an energy community in Poland depend on the organisational form chosen, the scale of operations and the ownership structure of the installation. In the case of energy cooperatives, it is necessary to incur formal costs related to registration, development of technical and legal documentation, preparation of the RES project, obtaining connection approvals, adaptation to the CSIRE system, integration with the data exchange platform and implementation of mechanisms for identification of users and transfer of metering data, as well as making investments in installations and meters.

For photovoltaic installations of 50–150 kW, which are typical for energy cooperatives, average investment costs range between approximately EUR 60,000 and EUR 115,000 (250-500 thousand PLN). The inclusion of energy storage systems can add a further EUR 25,000–70,000, depending on capacity (100-300 thousand PLN). Additional expenses include the implementation of billing systems, typically costing EUR 2,500–12,000, and the acquisition of remotely readable meters (from 10 to 50 thousand PLN).

Administrative costs include hiring a coordinator, accounting, legal services, maintenance and supervision of infrastructure. Annual operating costs for a small community can range from EUR 5,000 to EUR 23,000 (20K to 100K PLN), depending on the degree of automation of processes and the level of outsourcing.

In addition, communities using aggregators or providing flexibility services need to implement infrastructure to enable real-time communication (so-called secondary automation, consumption profile management), which can increase investment costs by another 10-20%. Implementing these solutions will be necessary if the community wishes to participate in the system services market.

In the case of clusters or OSEs with a more complex structure, the initial costs can reach up to EUR 230,000–460,000 (1-2 million PLN). Their reduction is possible thanks to cooperation with TSU, access to EU funds and use of ready-made organizational models.

3.4.9 Estimated profit margin

In Poland, the financial outlook for energy communities in 2025 is cautiously optimistic. While these initiatives are primarily designed to promote local sustainability and energy independence, they can also be financially viable, especially when well-planned and supported by incentives.

For communities focused on solar energy and energy sharing, profit margins typically range between 5% and 15% annually. This depends on several factors, including the scale of the project, access to grants or tax reliefs, and the ability to sell or offset energy through net billing. Communities that benefit from EU or national funding and manage their operations efficiently tend to see better returns.

However, profitability is not guaranteed. High upfront costs for equipment, grid connection, and administrative setup can delay financial gains. Moreover, smaller or less experienced groups may struggle with regulatory compliance and operational efficiency, which can reduce margins in the early years.

Despite these challenges, energy communities in Poland are increasingly seen as long-term financially and socially investments. With rising energy prices and growing public support, their potential for stable returns is improving, especially as the legal and financial environment continues to evolve.

The profit margin in energy community projects in Poland is not directly defined in commercial terms, since many of them operate on a non-profit basis. Nevertheless, the financial benefits of self-consumption, discounts and exemptions from system fees translate into real savings for community members.

According to estimates in RENALDO's materials, an energy cooperative can achieve effective savings of 20-40% over a G11 tariff, depending on its operating model, level of energy consumption and RES source mix. In models where the RES installation is a community asset and energy are billed according to the cost of generation, even a full return on investment within 7-10 years is possible.

In the case of communities using aggregation and participation in flexibility services, additional revenues are possible from the provision of balancing and demand reduction services. Estimated profit margins in such models range from 5 to 15% per year, depending on the price of energy and the technical capabilities of the participants.

The profit margin in energy community projects in Poland is not directly defined in commercial terms, since many of them operate on a non-profit basis. Nevertheless, the financial benefits of self-consumption, discounts and exemptions from system fees translate into real savings for community members.

An energy cooperative can achieve effective savings of 20-40% over the G11 tariff, depending on its operating model, level of energy consumption and RES source mix. In models where the RES installation is a community asset and energy are billed according to the cost of generation, even a full return on investment within 7-10 years is possible.

The introduction of CSIRE and the ability to participate in the market for flexibility services can further increase the profitability of communities. CSIRE will give communities access to billing using dynamic profiles, local balancing and dynamic tariffs. The potential margin from participation in balancing services (e.g., DSR, FFR) ranges from 5 to 15% per year, subject to appropriate IT and automation systems. In the future, once the OIRE platform services are fully operational, it will also be possible to introduce peer-to-peer trading models, which will open up new revenue streams for active communities.

3.5 Greece

3.5.1 Overview

Greece has been among the early adopters of regulatory frameworks supporting energy communities. Law No. 4513/2018^[84] defines the energy communities as cooperative entities serving social and solidarity objectives. These communities facilitate the engagement in energy production, supply, storage, and consumption. Law 5037/2023^[85] has amended the previous legal framework by aligning Greece more closely with the EU Directives 2018/2001 (RED II)^[1] and 2019/944^[2], through the formal introduction of Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs), and introduces the distinct legal categories of Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs). Under this law, the establishment of new energy communities under the previous legal regime is discontinued, while transitional provisions apply to existing entities. As a result, new energy community initiatives can no longer be registered under Law 4513/2018^[84], while existing communities are subject to specific transitional limitations regarding the development of new projects and access to support schemes. This transitional phase creates regulatory complexity and affects investment planning for both existing and prospective community actors.

In addition, the Greek framework reflects the transposition of the revised Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2023/2413 (RED III)^[10], adopted in late 2023, which reinforces enabling conditions for Renewable Energy Communities, including accelerated permitting procedures and obligations to simplify administrative processes. While RED III has been formally transposed at legislative level, several of its provisions relevant to energy sharing, market access, and digital integration remain dependent on secondary legislation and regulatory acts.

The Greek legislative model promotes participation by a wide spectrum of local actors including citizens, municipalities, and small-medium enterprises (SMEs); while establishing territorial criteria (e.g. 50%+1 of members must reside or be based in the region of the energy generation assets). Greece's early efforts and structural legal approach have assisted in energy communities' deployment. However, regulatory changes and market complexities are still challenging for the actors to participate or expand their activities.

3.5.2 Key trends

In recent years, Greece has made notable progress in modernising its legal framework for energy communities, aligning more closely with EU legislation. In the introduction of Law 5037/2023^[85], Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) are officially recognised by integrating concepts such as collective self-consumption and flexibility services into national law.

Another key development is the transition from the virtual net metering model to a virtual net billing scheme. Even though both mechanisms enable energy offsetting, virtual net billing introduces monetary compensation rather than pure energy balancing, affecting directly the interaction of participants with the grid and the market. While this legal innovation reflects an effort to align with evolving EU energy policies, it has also introduced uncertainty for community members and municipalities compared to earlier schemes^[86].

Although digital tools and smart metering are gradually being introduced, their integration into community-level energy sharing remains limited. Greece is progressing towards a more flexible and modern energy system, but implementation is still uneven, and many communities face technical, administrative, and financial challenges. This shift is further reinforced by secondary regulatory acts issued in 2023–2024 by RAAEY and HEDNO, which operationalise virtual net billing as the dominant mechanism for collective self-consumption, while postponing the introduction of real-time energy sharing pending advanced metering and settlement infrastructure^[87].

3.5.3 Legal framework-barriers and opportunities

Laws No. 4513/2018^[84] and No. 5037/2023^[85] outlines the legal structure, membership criteria and operational rights of energy communities. These includes provisions for energy generation, storage, supply, and participation in flexibility services. Moreover, the Greek regulatory framework includes participation thresholds and proximity criteria, such as the requirement that over 50% of members be local, supporting community control and inclusiveness.

Despite the significant progress, several obstacles restrict the full implementation of EU provisions. Energy sharing, as described in Article 15a of EU Directive 2019/944^[2] has not been directly transposed into national law. Instead, Greece still relies on virtual net billing schemes, facilitating energy offsetting through financial compensation. However, energy sharing is not established as a distinct legal right. In addition, the current legislative framework does not provide clear guidelines for the participation of third-party intermediaries, nor does it establish safeguards for vulnerable consumers, standardised contracts, or dispute resolution mechanisms. Market access for smaller communities is still limited, creating an imbalanced environment compared to larger energy actors. Moreover, while CECs are formally recognised, key rights such as the ability to operate distribution networks or participate fully in energy markets, are not yet fully enacted in practice.

Despite the formal transposition of EU Directives, Greece has not yet introduced a dedicated legal right to energy sharing as defined under Article 15a of Directive (EU) 2019/944^[2], as amended. Instead, collective arrangements remain limited to financial settlement mechanisms under virtual net billing. This partial transposition constrains the development of peer-to-peer energy exchange models and limits the contractual autonomy of energy communities.

Even though Greece's legal framework represents a solid foundation, it remains partially aligned with EU directives. To successfully support energy sharing and citizen participation, further legislative amendments are required, particularly in areas concerning consumer protection, market integration, and regulatory clarity.

3.5.4 Alignment with cybersecurity and data protection rules

Greece has fully implemented the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) across all sectors, including energy communities. In addition, the transposition of the NIS2 Directive has been completed through Law 5160/2024 (Official Government Gazette A' 195/2024)^[88], extending cybersecurity obligations to a wider range of energy-sector actors, including entities operating digital platforms and critical energy-related services.). Although it is fully applied across all sectors, including energy communities, the alignment with more recent legislative instruments, such as the NIS2 Directive, the Data Governance Act, and the proposed Data Act, remains limited in terms of energy communities and decentralised energy systems^[37].

There is currently no dedicated national framework that addresses straightforward the cybersecurity requirements for energy communities, including their interaction with digital platforms, smart meters, or third-party service providers^[37]. Similarly, the role of energy communities in data-sharing ecosystems is not clearly outlined, and the obligations for data access, interoperability, and digital transparency remain fragmented across different legislative acts.

The national Regulatory Authority for Energy (RAAEY) has some oversight over digital infrastructure in the energy sector, including consumer data handling by Distribution System Operators (DSOs) and energy suppliers. However, there is no centralised supervisory mechanism for energy communities. As a result, legal and technical gaps persist, especially in ensuring secure and standardised data flows within and between communities, and in addressing responsibilities for platform operators^[87].

Overall, Greece complies with core EU data protection laws, thus the specific transposition of cybersecurity and data governance requirements related to RECs and CECs is still underdeveloped. Dedicated legislative instruments and clearer institutional responsibilities will be needed to ensure safe, transparent, and interoperable digital environments for energy communities.

Although energy communities are not systematically classified as essential or important entities under NIS2, their increasing reliance on digital platforms, smart metering, and third-party service providers places them indirectly within the scope of heightened cybersecurity and risk-management expectations. However, no dedicated national guidance currently exists to clarify how NIS2 obligations should be proportionally applied to RECs and CECs, creating legal uncertainty for community operators and platform providers^[8].

3.5.5 Permit process

The permitting process for energy communities in Greece is relatively structured but depends on broader licensing procedures for renewable energy installations. The regulatory framework provides clear definitions for the establishment and operation of Energy Communities, RECs, and CECs, while it outlines the requirements for obtaining production, installation, and operation licenses. These procedures are managed primarily through the Regulatory Authority for Waste, Energy and Water (RAAEY) and the Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator (HEDNO)^[85, 87].

Though the regulatory pathway is defined, it is often described as administratively burdensome and time-consuming, especially for smaller communities or municipalities with limited technical capacity. The transition from net metering to virtual net billing has also introduced additional technical requirements that may complicate the permitting process related to grid connection and metering infrastructure^[86].

There is no specific procedure for energy communities, despite their social and environmental objectives. Although the legal framework allows collective self-consumption and virtual energy allocation, the deployment of these measures often requires several layers of approval, which slows down project development^[85].

Greece provides a legal basis for permitting energy communities, however there is absence of simplified procedures and digital coordination mechanisms limits the efficiency and accessibility of the process. Recent legislative initiatives aimed at accelerating renewable energy deployment, including spatial planning reforms and the designation of suitable areas for RES installations, have not yet resulted in simplified or fast-track permitting procedures specifically tailored to energy communities. As a result, RECs and CECs continue to be subject to the same procedural complexity as commercial RES developers, despite their social and non-profit character. Simplified licensing schemes and dedicated support mechanisms could promote the participation and accelerate the deployment^[89].

3.5.6 Status of the market

Greece has one of the most active energy-community ecosystems among Member States, largely due to early adoption of enabling legislation (L. 4513/2018^[84]) and strong public interest in collective RES development. The effectiveness of the new market design is further constrained by delays in the nationwide rollout of smart meters and the full operationalisation of digital settlement systems by HEDNO, which are prerequisites for granular energy sharing, dynamic pricing, and participation in flexibility markets. As of 2025, more than 1,500 energy communities are formally registered, with several hundred actives in renewable

generation, self-consumption, and energy-sharing schemes. Most Greek energy communities are still at the stage of developing PV parks for virtual net-metering, whereas more advanced models (storage-enabled communities, flexibility services, smart microgrids) are still emerging.

The Greek market shows strong regional concentration, with Western Macedonia, Crete, Thessaly, and the Peloponnese hosting most projects. Local authorities, agricultural cooperatives, SMEs, and civil society organisations are powerful founders. Even though participation from private households is increasing, it is still limited by administrative complexity and investment costs^[90].

The implementation of the new Electricity Market design^[91] (L.4951/2022) and the full transposition of RED II/III in 2023–2024 enhanced the framework for collective self-consumption and set the basis for energy sharing. However, the framework remains incomplete pending the adoption of secondary legislation and digital interface updates by Hellenic Electricity Distribution Operator (HEDNO). These are crucial for granular measurement and dynamic energy-sharing, which is still at an early stage, with large-scale deployment planned for 2025–2030. This delay limits the potential for real-time pricing, demand response, and communities' participation in flexibility markets. Nonetheless, several digital pilots (HEDNO flexibility platform, REC-based local flexibility trials, Horizon projects including CEEGS and FlexBIT) indicate a transition toward more advanced, data-rich community models^[85].

Overall, the Greek market demonstrates high social engagement and strong political support. However, it remains constrained by grid saturation, administrative complexity, slow digitalisation, and the absence of a fully operational energy-sharing framework.

3.5.7 Financial incentives

In Greece, financial support for community and collective self-consumption projects is delivered through a mix of investment grants (notably via RRF and national schemes), net-billing arrangements for collective self-consumption, and tax and subsidy windows targeting SMEs and vulnerable households. The practical attractiveness of each instrument depends on grid availability, connection timelines and the ability to document eligible costs.

Capital grants and subsidy programmes involve Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), Development Law (Law 4887/2022)^[92] incentives for Energy Communities, and Special subsidy windows for vulnerable groups. Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) contain "Photovoltaics on Roofs" & Storage Support. Greece allocates significant RRF resources to support rooftop PV and battery storage for households, farmers, SMEs, and energy-poor consumers^[93]. RECs can participate either as collective investors or through schemes that allocate a portion of production to vulnerable households. According to the Development Law (Law 4887/2022)^[92] incentives for Energy Communities, Energy Communities (ECs and RECs) are eligible for capital subsidies, leasing subsidies, and tax exemptions for renewable projects, energy-efficiency upgrades, and storage facilities. Projects implemented by RECs benefit from higher subsidy rates, especially in less developed regions (Aegean islands, mountainous areas, and remote municipalities). In Greece, vulnerable groups are benefited by special subsidy windows. Several national schemes focus on energy-poor households when they participate through an Energy Community. Subsidies may cover up to 60–100% of installation costs, depending on the socioeconomic category

Regarding tax incentives, it seems that Energy Community RES projects may benefit from reduced corporate income tax or partial exemptions under the Development Law, accelerated depreciation for renewable energy and storage equipment, and reduced VAT for RES installations under certain eligibility conditions. These taxes also benefit significantly by reducing upfront capital expenses^[92].

The EU offers targeted incentives funded by the EU itself. The European Regional Development Fund (ERDF, 2021–2027) supports local RES projects, energy-efficiency upgrades, and digitalisation of distribution networks. Many regional ERDF programmes include priority axes explicitly devoted to Energy Communities.

Greece is a major beneficiary of the Just Transition Fund (JTF) due to lignite phase-out. This organisation supports Energy Communities in Western Macedonia and Megalopolis, offering grants for RES, energy sharing, storage, and innovative local energy systems^[94]. Through LIFE^[95] & Horizon programmes^[96], Europe provides technical assistance grants for the formation of RECs, development of business models, digital tools, and community engagement structures.

In regional level, there are several incentives for municipalities participating in RECs. Municipalities can join or create Energy Communities to develop PV parks or local RES projects. These benefit from priority in spatial planning approvals, higher reimbursement rates for RES investments, and dedicated JTF and RRF windows for municipal RECs. Many municipal RECs dedicate part of the production to low-income households at zero or heavily discounted cost.

While Greece offers generous financial support, practical limitations and challenges still exist. The main obstacles are constituted by long waiting times for grid connection approvals, rapid saturation of distribution grid capacity in several regions, high interest rates for borrowing by newly established RECs, and significant administrative burdens and complexity in meeting eligibility documentation.

3.5.8 Cost of implementation

The [Table 3.7](#) below summarises capital, administrative, and operational costs that are associated with deployment and running Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) in Greece. These estimates the current market structure, legal context, and readiness of supporting infrastructure (smart meters, billing systems, digital tools)^[85, 97].

Table 3.7: Cost Structure for Implementing Energy Communities in Greece

COST CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	TYPICAL COST RANGE
Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)	Purchase and installation of renewable energy assets (PV, batteries, inverters). Costs vary by scale, site, and technology.	Small-to-medium PV (100–500 kW): €120,000–€600,000.
		Medium-scale PV (0.5–1 MW): €450,000–€900,000.
Grid Connection Costs	Connection fees, reinforcement charges, and metering infrastructure required by HEDNO. These costs depend heavily on local hosting capacity.	From €3,000–€25,000 for small installations; significantly higher for MW-scale projects or constrained networks.
Digital Infrastructure	Smart meters, community energy management platforms, remote monitoring, cybersecurity measures, and compliance with future Data Act requirements.	Smart meters: €100–€180 per member (ongoing national roll-out)
		Digital platforms: €10,000–€40,000 depending on functionality.
		Cybersecurity compliance: €5,000–€20,000 for initial setup.
Administrative Set-up costs	Establishment of the cooperative entity, legal documentation, statutes, accounting registration, and regulatory filings.	€3,000–€10,000 depending on legal support required and complexity of membership structure.
Licensing & Permitting costs	Documentation preparation, engineering studies, environmental screening (where applicable), and submissions to RAAEY/HEDNO.	€5,000–€30,000 for small-to-medium projects. Costs rise with location constraints and interconnection complexity
Operational Expenditure (OPEX)	Annual accounting, audits, cooperative management, IT maintenance, insurance, and grid charges.	€15,000–€60,000 per year depending on size, outsourcing level, and digitalisation.

Virtual Net Billing Compliance Costs	Technical and administrative procedures for settlement, billing compatibility, and metering verification.	Typically, €2,000–€10,000 initial setup, plus annual maintenance fees depending on the billing provider.
Additional Costs for Flexibility Services	Infrastructure to enable real-time data exchange, automation, and control required to participate in system services in future markets.	An additional €10,000–€25,000 for automation and control infrastructure.

The establishment of an energy community in Greece requires considerable upfront investment, particularly in view of the transition from virtual net metering to virtual net billing, which introduces new requirements for advanced metering and settlement. Capital costs remain in the largest category, especially for communities deploying mid-scale PV or storage. Administrative and compliance costs, including cooperative formation, billing setup, technical studies, and licensing procedures, are also significant due to Greece’s complex permitting environment.

Digitalisation costs are expected to grow. Additional requirements arising from NIS2, the Data Governance Act, and the Data Act will influence communities’ future IT architecture. Annual operational costs depend on whether communities outsource management or develop in-house capacity, with smaller organisations typically facing proportionally higher expenses.

3.5.9 Estimated profit margin

The [Table 3.8](#) below provides an overview of the expected profitability of Greek energy communities, based on current regulatory conditions, energy prices, and financial incentives^[97].

Table 3.8: Estimated Profit Margins for Greek RECs/CECs

PROFITABILITY COMPONENT	DESCRIPTION	ESTIMATED RANGE
Annual Profit Margin (typical solar based REC/CEC)	Net margin after covering OPEX, debt servicing (if any), and reserve funds.	5%–12% typical range for mature communities. Higher margins require grants or tax reliefs.
Impact of Virtual Net Billing	Virtual net billing replaces pure energy offsetting with financial compensation. Profitability now depends on energy market prices rather than kWh balancing.	Higher volatility; margins may fall to 3%–7% for communities without grants or subsidies.
Effect of Grants (RRF, Development Law, local programmes)	Reduces capital expenditure and improves payback period.	Communities receiving subsidies can reach 10%–15% margins. Payback periods drop from 10–12 years to 6–8 years.
Energy Poverty Support Schemes	RECs supporting vulnerable households may access additional incentives but usually reinvest profits instead of distributing them.	Margin becomes non-financial, oriented toward social benefit rather than revenue.
Large-scale Municipal RECs	Municipalities often benefit from economies of scale, better financing terms, and access to public land.	Margins in the 8%–14% range, depending on project design.
Participation in Future Flexibility Markets	When fully implemented in Greece, flexibility services could provide new revenue streams (e.g., demand response, local balancing).	Potential additional 5%–10% revenue, but contingent on regulatory reform and digital readiness.

Profit margins for Greek energy communities span a wide range depending on project size, financing approach, and access to subsidies. Communities relying solely on virtual net billing without grants may

experience modest returns due to the tie of settlements to market prices, rather than stable offsetting mechanisms. Even though communities benefit national and EU funding, especially through the Recovery and Resilience Facility, can significantly increase profitability, shorten payback periods, and strengthen long-term financial viability. Municipal energy communities often achieve higher stability due to economies of scale and administrative capacity.

Emerging opportunities in flexibility services could improve future margins. However, these markets are not yet operational in Greece. As digital infrastructure matures and regulatory adjustments are made, Greek RECs and CECs may support the existence of new revenue streams beyond energy production alone.

4 Comparative Analysis and Findings

Across the five FlexBIT jurisdictions, a number of ongoing technical, legal, and institutional barriers limit the ability of energy communities for secure data exchange, participating in flexibility markets, or engaging with DSOs and aggregators in real time.

4.1 Interoperability and data exchange challenges

Regarding the technical challenges, the fragmented digital infrastructures are noticed in Malta and Poland. These lack fully operational energy data hubs, leading to asynchronous data access and significant administrative burden. Smart metering is notably developed in Italy and Germany. However, Poland and Malta appear to be significantly behind, which demonstrated limited real-time monitoring, dynamic tariffs, and demand-response participation. DSOs use heterogeneous metering, billing, and communication protocols, resulting in complicated cross-platform integration and collective self-consumption models. These indicate that interoperability standards are still limited. Cybersecurity faces important gaps. Many communities rely solely on legacy ICT architecture without including NIS2-class risk management, increasing the vulnerability to data breaches and operational disruptions.

The EU Directives RED II^[1], RED III^[10] and Directive 2019/944^[2] has partially been transposed to EU's Member States legal systems. Malta and Germany, the practices of energy sharing are not yet fully implemented. The distribution of data-controller responsibilities under GDPR is unclear, especially for multi-actor platforms involving DSOs, aggregators, and REC/CEC administrators. Standardised data access rules in alignment with the Data Act are absent, especially concerning third-party access, FRAND conditions, and user-authorized data sharing. Heterogeneous permitting and licensing rules complicate the replication of digital services across borders.

Market and operational challenges arise due to limited incentives for local flexibility, reducing the value proposition of digital community platforms. Low digital readiness among community members (SMEs, households) inhibits the adoption of advanced energy-management tools. The alignment of DSOs' investment plans with data exchange needs of community initiatives is considered insufficient.

In summary, the analysis reveals that whereas the regulatory foundations for RECs and CECs exist, interoperability remains limited, resulting in technical and institutional bottlenecks that FlexBIT intends to highlight through a harmonised, cyber-secure data-exchange framework.

4.2 Alignment with FlexBIT goals

FlexBIT's principal goals include interoperability, secure data exchange, regulatory compliance, and digital empowerment of communities, which directly address the gaps identified in the comparative assessment.

FlexBIT's architecture aligns with the Data Act's principles for user-authorized data access, third-party data-sharing mechanisms, and cloud-interoperability requirements, demonstrating an area of strong alignment regarding the energy data interoperability. FlexBIT's cybersecurity plan integrates NIS2-aligned practices, incident reporting protocols, and risk-management frameworks, addressing national gaps identified especially in Malta and Poland. The collective self-consumption and flexibility markets are supported by the FlexBIT. The project's platform facilitates secure communication between DSOs, aggregators, and communities, supporting RED II/III provisions. In addition, FlexBIT provides templates and reference models that can reduce or even eliminate the administrative complexity and legal uncertainty for new RECs/CECs

However, there are areas requiring strategic attention. FlexBIT must guarantee flexible API-based integration with older metering systems especially in Malta and Poland, promoting the compatibility with heterogeneous

smart-meter infrastructures. Countries like Germany (SMGW system) and Italy (TIAD framework) have established national rules requiring customised integration layers. Permitting and registration workflows should be improved while FlexBIT should remain adaptable to different national REC/CEC registration procedures. It is obvious that significant differences in incentives across the five countries regarding their financial viability models may affect FlexBIT's adoption rates unless financing toolkits are integrated

Overall, the cross-country analysis confirms that FlexBIT addresses genuine and widespread regulatory and digitalisation gaps and has high replicability potential.

5 Conclusions and policy recommendations

This chapter consolidates the cross-country findings and translates them into targeted actions for EU institutions, Member States, DSOs and energy communities, focusing on data interoperability, market access, and cybersecurity compliance.

5.1 Key findings

Across Italy, Germany, Malta, Poland, and Greece, several common conclusions emerge. The EU demonstrates a strong framework but uneven national transposition. EU directives (RED II/III[1, 10], 2019/944^[2], 2019/943^[20]) provide substantial foundations for RECs/CECs, yet implementation remains uneven. Energy-sharing provisions, prosumer rights, and market-access rules vary considerably by country.

Digitalisation is a critical bottleneck for smart-meter deployment; DSO data systems, and national digital platforms are inconsistent. The absence of interoperability and standardisation results in significant restrictions on data exchange and flexibility participation. Cybersecurity obligations will increase sharply under NIS2 Directive[8]. However, most community-level actors are unprepared for the upcoming risk-management and reporting requirements, while national cybersecurity frameworks vary, increasing compliance complexity.

Financial incentives demonstrate variable differences. For example, Italy and Greece offer structured REC support, while Malta provides almost none. The European funding sources of RRF and ERDF contribute to the Digital-infrastructure support (smart grids, AML, digital substations). The high administrative burdens limit scalability. This is the major reason for complex permitting, licensing, and community-formation rules, which are still a significant barrier. Lack of standardised procedures creates delays and increases transaction costs.

Political support is broadly in place, but operational implementation (data access, interoperable interfaces, and clear procedures) remains limited.

5.2 Policy and regulatory recommendations

In terms of EU Institutions, they can accelerate harmonisation of data-exchange standards, expanding the Energy Data Space into a mandatory interoperability framework for DSOs and energy community platforms. Secondary legislation should be issued under the Data Act specifically clarifying rules for energy-sector FRAND data access. Moreover, they could implement an EU-wide guidance on energy sharing, defining principles for tariffs, metering, and grid-use calculations and create a dedicated EU programme for digitalisation of distribution networks supporting real-time data flows and cybersecurity compliance.

Each Member State should act in fully transpose RED III[10] and Directive 2019/944^[2] with clear definitions, processes, and rights for RECs and CECs. It would be beneficial for EU States to establish national energy data hubs interoperable with FlexBIT architectures. Also, they should move forward to simplify the procedures of permitting and one-stop shops for community formation, registration, and grid connection. Finally, they could provide targeted funding for digital tools (metering upgrades, IoT devices, EMS, cybersecurity systems).

Distribution System Operators (DSOs) should be responsible for implementing data-sharing APIs aligned with Data Act principles and FlexBIT's interoperability standards. The incorporation of community-based flexibility into network planning includes regional price signals and congestion management tools. DSOs would also promote the strengthening of cybersecurity capabilities and coordinate with communities on incident-response protocols.

Energy Communities should adopt governance structures that support data protection, transparent benefit-sharing, and compliance with cybersecurity obligations, while investing in digital energy management systems and smart-metering tools. Energy Communities’ partnership with DSOs and aggregators will allow them to participate in local flexibility markets.

5.3 Implementation roadmap for FlexBIT

FlexBIT enables specific opportunities by turning legal requirements into implementable technical building blocks: standardised interfaces for data exchange, role-based access controls, and cybersecurity-by-design patterns that can be adopted by communities and system operators. Beyond addressing existing regulatory and technical gaps, the project enables new forms of participation, value creation, and system optimisation across residential, tertiary, and industrial buildings. Figure 5.1 illustrates the main opportunity areas enabled by the FlexBIT framework, spanning market participation, grid operation, digital innovation, cybersecurity, and socio-economic impact.

Figure 5.1: Overview of key opportunities enabled by the FlexBIT framework for energy communities, system operators, digital platforms, and local stakeholders.

A core opportunity introduced by FlexBIT lies in enabling energy communities to move beyond static self-consumption models and actively participate in local and regional flexibility markets. By establishing interoperable interfaces between community platforms, aggregators, and Distribution System Operators (DSOs), FlexBIT lowers the technical and organisational barriers that currently prevent communities from offering demand-response, storage-based flexibility, and load-shifting services. This allows communities to monetise flexibility from aggregated residential, tertiary, and small industrial assets, transforming them from passive consumers into active system participants.

FlexBIT supports DSOs and TSOs by enabling access to decentralised flexibility resources in a secure and standardised manner. Through real-time or near-real-time data exchange, local flexibility services can be used as an alternative to traditional grid reinforcement, particularly in areas facing congestion, hosting-capacity constraints, or rapid renewable deployment. This creates opportunities for cost-efficient grid

operation, deferred infrastructure investments, and enhanced system resilience, while simultaneously creating new revenue streams for community-based assets.

The project provides a practical pathway for implementing interoperable digital architectures aligned with the Data Act, GDPR, and the forthcoming Common European Energy Data Space. FlexBIT demonstrates how standardised APIs, role-based access control, and secure data-sharing mechanisms can be deployed across different national contexts. This creates opportunities for platform providers, aggregators, and technology developers to scale solutions across Member States, reducing fragmentation and enabling cross-border replication of energy community models.

By embedding cybersecurity-by-design principles in line with NIS2 and the Network Code on Cybersecurity, FlexBIT strengthens trust in digitally enabled energy communities. Clear allocation of responsibilities between communities, platform operators, and system operators reduces legal uncertainty and system liability risks. This increased trust is a prerequisite for broader participation by citizens, SMEs, and municipalities, and for the uptake of advanced digital services such as automated flexibility activation and data-driven optimisation.

FlexBIT contributes to simplifying compliance with complex EU legal requirements by translating high-level regulatory obligations into operational workflows and technical design choices. This reduces administrative burdens for community initiatives, particularly smaller or newly established entities that lack regulatory expertise. The resulting clarity lowers entry barriers, supports faster project development, and improves the bankability of community-based energy projects.

By enabling collective flexibility, energy sharing, and data-driven optimisation, FlexBIT supports local value creation and energy-cost reduction. Energy communities can improve self-sufficiency, reduce exposure to volatile wholesale prices, and channel economic benefits toward vulnerable households, municipalities, or local SMEs. These mechanisms directly contribute to energy poverty mitigation, social acceptance of renewable energy projects, and inclusive participation in the energy transition.

Finally, FlexBIT offers significant opportunities for policymakers and regulators. The project generates evidence on how interoperable, cyber-secure, and digitally enabled energy communities can operate across diverse regulatory and infrastructural contexts. This supports policy learning, informs future legislative updates, and contributes to the harmonisation of national frameworks. The FlexBIT approach can serve as a reference model for future EU initiatives aiming to integrate decentralised flexibility and community energy into the internal electricity market.

6 References

1. Directive (EU) 2018/2001 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources, in 2018/2001. 2018, L 328/82, 21.12.2018.
2. Directive (EU) 2019/944 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on common rules for the internal market for electricity and amending Directive 2012/27/EU in 2019/944 2019, L 158/126 14.6.2019.
3. European Commission, *Communication From The Commission To The European Parliament, The European Council, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions. The European Green Deal. COM(2019) 640 final.* 2019, European Commission, : Brussels.
4. Council, E. *Fit for 55.* 2025; Available from: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/fit-for-55/>.
5. *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the regions-REPowerEU Plan* in SWD(2022) 230 final. 2022.
6. EU, R., *Annual report 2024-European federation of energy communities.* 2024.
7. Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act) in 2023/2854. 2023, L. 22.12.2023.
8. Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive) in PE/32/2022/REV/2. 2022, OJ L 333, 27.12.2022, . p. 80-152.
9. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), in 2016/679. 2016, L 119/1, 4.5.2016.
10. Directive (EU) 2023/2413 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 October 2023 amending Directive (EU) 2018/2001, Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 and Directive 98/70/EC as regards the promotion of energy from renewable sources, and repealing Council Directive (EU) 2015/652 (RED III), in 2023/2413 2023, L. 31.10.2023.
11. Agency, I.E., *Net Zero by 2050 A Roadmap for the Global Energy Sector*, I.E. Agency, Editor. 2021.
12. IRENA, *Community Energy Benefits-Powering Universal Wellbeing.* 2024.
13. *Testo Integrato Autoconsumo Diffuso (TIAD) – Autoconsumo diffuso: configurazioni e valorizzazione*, in *Delibera 727/2022/R/eel.* 2022, ARERA (Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente).
14. CMS. *Renewable Energy in Italy.* 2024; Available from: https://cms.law/en/int/expert-guides/cms-expert-guide-to-renewable-energy/italy/#_4-Self-consumption-systems-in-Italy.
15. FFE. *How is the German Smart Meter Rollout Progressing? Evaluation of the rollout as of March 31.* 2025. 2025.
16. *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions- Powering a climate-neutral economy: An EU Strategy for Energy System Integration*, in COM(2020) 299 final. 2020.
17. *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions-Digitalising the energy system - EU action plan*, in COM(2022) 552 final. 2022.
18. *Common European Energy Data Space.* 2023: Publications Office of the European Union.
19. Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act) in PE/85/2021/REV/1. 2022, OJ L 152, 3.6.2022.
20. Regulation (EU) 2019/943 on the internal market for electricity, in 2019/943. 2019, L 158/54, 14.6.2019.

21. *Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 September 2022 on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector and amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act)*, in 2022/1925. 2022, L. 12.10.2022.
22. *Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2024/1366 of 11 March 2024 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2019/943 of the European Parliament and of the Council by establishing a network code on sector-specific rules for cybersecurity aspects of cross-border electricity flows*, in 2024/1366. 2024, C/2024/1383.
23. *Directive (EU) 2023/1971 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2023 on energy efficiency and amending Regulation (EU) 2023/995*, in 2023/1791 2023.
24. Draghi, M., *The future of European competitiveness Part A: A competitiveness strategy for Europe*. 2024.
25. Draghi, M., *The future of European competitiveness Part B: In-depth analysis and recommendations*. 2024.
26. De La Feld, S. *EU energy report, the italian paradox: leader in clean-tech production, but still too dependent on fossil fuels*. 2025; Available from: <https://www.eunews.it/en/2024/09/11/eu-energy-report-italy-fails-leader-in-clean-tech-production-but-still-too-dependent-on-fossil-fuels/>.
27. *Decreto 16 maggio 2025 — Modifiche al decreto del Ministro dell'ambiente e della sicurezza energetica 7 dicembre 2023, n. 414 (Comunità energetiche rinnovabili / autoconsumo collettivo)*. 2025, Repubblica Italiana — Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica (MASE).
28. *Decreto Legislativo 8 novembre 2021, n. 199 — Attuazione della direttiva (UE) 2018/2001 del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio, dell'11 dicembre 2018, sulla promozione dell'uso dell'energia da fonti rinnovabili*, in *Decreto Legislativo n. 199/2021*. 2021: Italy.
29. *Decreto Legislativo 8 novembre 2021, n. 210 — Attuazione della direttiva UE 2019/944, del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio, del 5 giugno 2019, relativa a norme comuni per il mercato interno dell'energia elettrica e che modifica la direttiva 2012/27/UE, nonché recante disposizioni per l'adeguamento della normativa nazionale alle disposizioni del regolamento UE 943/2019 sul mercato interno dell'energia elettrica e del regolamento UE 941/2019 sulla preparazione ai rischi nel settore dell'energia elettrica e che abroga la direttiva 2005/89/CE. (21G00233)*, in *D.Lgs. n. 210/2021*. 2021: Italy.
30. *Decreto del Ministro dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica 7 dicembre 2023, n. 414 — Individuazione di una tariffa incentivante per impianti a fonti rinnovabili inseriti in comunità energetiche rinnovabili e nelle configurazioni di autoconsumo singolo a distanza e collettivo*, in *D.M. n. 414/2023*. 2023, Repubblica Italiana — Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica (MASE).
31. (MEF), M.d.E.e.d.F., *The Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR – Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza)*. 2021.
32. European Commission, *Commission approves an Italian State aid scheme to support renewable electricity production to foster the transition to a net-zero economy*. 2024.
33. Agency, I.E., *Italy 2023-Energy Policy Review*. 2023.
34. Eurostat, *EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC)*. 2023.
35. Moretti, E. and E. Stamponi, *The Renewable Energy Communities in Italy and the Role of Public Administrations: The Experience of the Municipality of Assisi between Challenges and Opportunities*. Sustainability, 2023. **15**(15): p. 11869.
36. *Decreto Legislativo 3 luglio 2021-Decreto Aree Idonee elaborato dal Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica*. 2024.
37. REScoop.EU, *Enabling Frameworks & Support Schemes*. 2025.
38. European Commission, *Assessment of the draft updated National Energy and Climate Plan of Italy*. 2029.
39. *Decreto-Legge 21 settembre 2019, n. 105 — Disposizioni urgenti in materia di perimetro di sicurezza nazionale cibernetica*, in *D.L. n. 105/2019 (convertito in L. 133/2019)*. 2019, Gazzetta Ufficiale della Repubblica Italiana.

40. *Attuazione della direttiva (UE) 2016/1148 del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio, del 6 luglio 2016, recante misure per un livello comune elevato di sicurezza delle reti e dei sistemi informativi nell'Unione. (18G00092), in D.Lgs. n. 65/2018. 2018, Gazzetta Ufficiale / Normattiva.*
41. *Aggiornamento dei corrispettivi di dispacciamento dal 1 gennaio 2020, in Delibera ARERA 574/2019/R/eel. 2019, Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente.*
42. *Attuazione della direttiva (UE) 2019/1024 relativa all'apertura dei dati e al riutilizzo dell'informazione del settore pubblico (rifusione), in D.Lgs. n. 200/2021 (GU Serie Generale n. 285 del 30-11-2021 – S.O. n. 42). 2021, Gazzetta Ufficiale / Normattiva.*
43. (GSE), G.S.E. *Decreto Comunità Energetiche Rinnovabili. 2023.*
44. Europei, I.C. *Building renewable energy communities in Emilia-Romagna: Empowering local action with digital ambassadors. 2025.*
45. *Taxonomy Regulation (EU) 2020/852, in 2020/852 2020, L 198/13, 22.6.2020.*
46. normativa,, S. *TSI "Faster Permitting for Renewable Energy Projects in Italy" – avvio delle attività. 2024; Available from: <https://www.semplificazonenormativa.gov.it/it/comunicazione/notizie/tsi-faster-permitting-for-renewable-energy-projects-in-italy-avvio-delle-attivita/>.*
47. Monegato, S., *Renewable Energy Communities in Italy: The Challenges of Public Governance. 2025.*
48. Legambiente. *Rinnovabili, Italia in ritardo. I dati di Legambiente. 2024; Available from: <https://www.legambiente.it/comunicati-stampa/rinnovabili-italia-in-ritardo-i-dati-di-legambiente>.*
49. Legambiente. *Legambiente presenta Comuni Rinnovabili 2024. 2024; Available from: <https://www.legambiente.it/comunicati-stampa/legambiente-presenta-comuni-rinnovabili-2024>.*
50. European Commission, *State of the Energy Union Report 2024. 2024.*
51. (MASE), M.d.A.e.d.S.E., *Relazione sulla situazione energetica nazionale 2023, D.E.D.G.F.E.e.T. Abilitativi, Editor. 2024.*
52. Milano, E.S.G.P.d., *Renewable Energy Report 2024. 2024.*
53. Energetici, G.S., *DECRETO CACER e TIAD – Regole operative per l'accesso al servizio per l'autoconsumo diffuso e al contributo PNRR. 2025.*
54. (Berlin), A.E., *Die Energiewende in Deutschland: Stand der Dinge 2024. 2024: Berlin.*
55. (dena), D.E.-A.G., *Energy communities: Accelerators of the decentralised energy transition. 2022.*
56. Boos, T.H., M.; Wegerich, P., *Energy sharing in Germany: Status and gaps. 2021.*
57. Ahlemeyer, K.G., Kai-Michael; Wawe, Tim; Siebenhüner, Bernd, *Success factors of citizen energy cooperatives in north western Germany: a conceptual and empirical review. Energy, Sustainability and Society, 2022. 12(29).*
58. Frick, V.F., Julia; Anger, Kathrin; Knörzer, Ulrike; Tornow, Maren; Schnee, Hannah, *Mit Suffizienz zur Energiewende: Wie Energiegenossenschaften Verbrauchsreduktion in Haushalten fördern können, in Schriftenreihe des IÖW, Nr. 224/22. 2022: Berlin.*
59. *Gesetz betreffend die Erwerbs- und Wirtschaftsgenossenschaften (Genossenschaftsgesetz – GenG), in BGBl. I S. 2230. 2006: Germany.*
60. *Act on the Development of Renewable Energy Sources (Renewable Energy Sources Act - RES Act 2014). 2014: Germany.*
61. *Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG 2017). 2017: Germany.*
62. Kahla, F.H., Lars; Müller, Jakob R.; Degenhart, Heinrich, *Development and State of Community Energy Companies and Energy Cooperatives in Germany, in Munich Personal RePEc Archive. 2017, Leuphana University of Lüneburg.*
63. Hauser, E.e.a., *Auction design and actor diversity in the EEG. 2015.*

64. Clearingstelle EEG | KWKG (Commissioned by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, B., *Gesetz für den Ausbau erneuerbarer Energien (Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz – EEG 2023)*. 2023: Berlin.
65. Background, T., *Plans to accelerate smart meter rollout and digitisation*. 2022.
66. *Gesetz über die Elektrizitäts- und Gasversorgung (Energiewirtschaftsgesetz – EnWG)*, in *BGBI. I S. 1970*. 2005: Germany.
67. (DGRV), D.G.-u.R.e.V., *Zahlen und Fakten der Genossenschaften in Deutschland 2023*. 2023, DGRV – Deutscher Genossenschafts- und Raiffeisenverband e.V.: Berlin.
68. *Gesetz über den Schutz personenbezogener Daten bei der Datenverarbeitung (Bundesdatenschutzgesetz – BDSG)*, in *BGBI. I p. 1858; 2022 I p. 1045*. 2017: Germany.
69. *Zweites Gesetz zur Erhöhung der Sicherheit informationstechnischer Systeme (IT-Sicherheitsgesetz 2.0)*, in *BGBI. I 2021 S. 1122*. 2021: Germany.
70. *Verordnung zur Bestimmung Kritischer Infrastrukturen nach dem Gesetz über das Bundesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnik (BSI-KritisV)*, in *BGBI. I S. 958*. 2016: Germany.
71. Holstenkamp, L.M., J., *Cooperative models in German energy supply*. 2013.
72. *Competitive Bidding Rules for Renewable Sources of Energy Installations (Capacity from 40kW up to less than 1000kW) Regulations*, in *S.L. 545.32*. 2020: Malta.
73. *Regulator for Energy and Water Services Act*, in *CAP. 545*. 2015: Malta.
74. *Data Protection Act*, in *CAP. 586*. 2018: Malta.
75. *Development Planning Act*, in *CAP.522*. 2016: Malta.
76. *Renewable Energy Sources*. 2015: Poland.
77. *Energy Law*. 1997: Poland.
78. *Energy Law (updated)*. 2023.
79. *General Data Protection Regulation (RODO)*. 2016: Poland.
80. *Cooperative Law*. 1982: Poland.
81. (URE), P.E.R.O. *Register of energy clusters (Rejestr Klastrow Energii)*. 2024; Available from: <https://bip.ure.gov.pl/bip/rejestr-y-bazy/klastry/4608,Rejestr-Klastrow-Energii.html>.
82. (URE), P.E.R.O., *Register of energy cooperatives in Poland*. 2025.
83. (URE), P.E.R.O., *Register of citizen energy communities in Poland*. 2025.
84. *Energy Communities and other provisions*, in *Greek Law No. 4513*. 2018, Government Gazette A' 9/23.01.2018: Greece.
85. *Renaming of the Regulatory Authority for Energy to Regulatory Authority for Waste, Energy and Water and expansion of its scope to include responsibilities over water services and municipal waste management – Strengthening of water policy – Modernization of legislation on the use and production of electricity from renewable energy sources through the incorporation of Directives (EU) 2018/2001 and 2019/944 – Specific provisions for renewable energy sources and environmental protection.*, in *Greek Law No. 5037*. 2023, Government Gazette A' 78/28.03.2023: Greece.
86. *Amendment and replacement of Ministerial Decision No. ΥΠΕΝ/ΔΑΠΕΕΚ/15084/382/19.02.2019 "Installation of generation plants by self-producers under the application of energy net metering or virtual net metering in accordance with Article 14A of Law 3468/2006, as in force, and by Energy Communities under the application of virtual net metering in accordance with Article 11 of Law 4513/2018" (Official Government Gazette B' 759)*. in *Ministerial Decision No. ΥΠΕΝ/ΔΑΠΕΕΚ/93976/2772*. 2024, Government Gazette B/ 5074/5.09.2024.
87. *On the operation of Electricity and Natural Gas Energy Markets, on the Exploration, Production and Transmission Networks of Hydrocarbons, and other provisions.*, in *Greek Law No. 4001*. 2011, Government Gazette A' 179/22.08.2011: Greece.

88. *Transposition of Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive), and other provisions.*, in Greek Law No 5160. 2024, Government Gazette A' 195/27.11.2024.
89. *Modernization of environmental legislation, incorporation into Greek law of Directives 2018/844 and 2019/692 of the European Parliament and of the Council, and other provisions.*, in Law No. 4685. 2020, Government Gazette A' 92/7.05.2020.
90. *Ministry for the Environment and Energy, Just Transition Development Plan (SDAM) of the Region of Western Macedonia and the Municipality of Megalopolis in the post-lignite era.* 2020.
91. *Modernisation of the Renewable Energy Sources (RES) permitting process – Phase B, licensing for electricity generation and storage, framework for the development of Pilot Offshore Floating Photovoltaic Stations, and specific provisions on energy and environmental protection.*, in Greek Law No. 4951. 2022, Government Gazette B' 129/04.07.2022.
92. *Development Law – Greece Strong Growth*, in Greek Law No. 4887. 2022, Government Gazette A' 16/04.02.2022.
93. *COUNCIL IMPLEMENTING DECISION amending the Implementing Decision of 13 July 2021 on the approval of the assessment of the recovery and resilience plan for Greece*, in 15754/25. 2025.
94. *Regulation (EU) 2021/1060 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 June 2021 laying down common provisions on the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund Plus, the Cohesion Fund, the Just Transition Fund and the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund and financial rules for those and for the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund, the Internal Security Fund and the Instrument for Financial Support for Border Management and Visa Policy.*, in PE/47/2021/INIT. 2021, OJ L 231, 30.6.2021, pp. 159–706
95. *Regulation (EU) 2021/783 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2021 establishing a Programme for the Environment and Climate Action (LIFE), and repealing Regulation (EU) No 1293/2013* in PE/14/2021/INIT. 2021, OJ L 172, 17.5.2021, pp. 53–78.
96. *Regulation (EU) 2021/695 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013* in PE/12/2021/INIT. 2021, OJ L 170, 12.5.2021, pp. 1–68
97. Tank, T.G., *Energy Communities & Self-Production in Greece #7.* 2025.

7 Appendices

7.1 Table of national legislation

COUNTRY	LEGISLATION	YEAR	TYPE	NOTES
Italy	Legislative Decree 199/2021 – RED II Transposition	2021	Legislative decree	Legal basis for Renewable and Citizen Energy Communities
Italy	ARERA Resolution 727/2022/R/eel – TIAD	2022	Regulatory authority resolution	Integrated framework for distributed self-consumption
Italy	MASE Decree No. 414/2023 – CACER Decree	2023	Ministerial decree	Operational and incentive framework for energy communities
Germany	Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG)	2023	Federal law	Support framework for renewables and citizen energy
Germany	Energy Industry Act (EnWG)	2024	Federal law	Market regulation and grid access rules
Germany	Tenant Electricity Act (Mieterstromgesetz)	2023	Federal law	Legal basis for collective self-consumption in buildings
Malta	Electricity Market Regulations (S.L. 545:34)	2022	Subsidiary legislation	Collective self-consumption and consumer protection
Malta	Energy and Water Agency Act	2021	Primary law	Institutional framework for energy regulation
Poland	Renewable Energy Sources Act (RES Act)	2023	National law	Framework for energy cooperatives and clusters
Poland	Energy Law Act	2024	National law	Electricity market rules and grid operation
Poland	Act on Energy Cooperatives Amendment	2025	National law	Expansion of cooperative eligibility and territorial scope
Greece	Law 4513/2018 – Energy Communities	2018	Primary law	Initial legal framework for Energy Communities
Greece	Law 5037/2023 – Introduction of RECs and CFCs (RED II/III)	2023	Primary law	Aligns national law with RED II/III; transitional regime
Greece	Law 4951/2022 – Electricity Market Design Reform	2022	Primary law	Electricity market reform and RES acceleration
Greece	Law 4887/2022 – Development Law	2022	Primary law	Investment incentives and tax reliefs for RECs
Greece	Law 5160/2024 – NIS2 Transposition	2024	Primary law	Cybersecurity obligations for energy-sector entities
Greece	Ministerial Decision YΠEN/ΔΑΠΕΕΚ/15084/382/2019 – Virtual Net Metering	2019	Ministerial decision	Rules for self-production and virtual net metering